

ASILE

Global Asylum
Governance and
the European
Union's Role

Responsibility Allocation and UN GCR Implementation

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ACHPR	African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights
ARIO	Articles on the Responsibility of International Organizations
ARSIWA	Articles on the Responsibility of States for Internationally Wrongful Acts
CEDAW	Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination Against Women
CFREU	Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union
COI	Country of Origin Information
CRC	Convention on the Rights of the Child
EASO	European Asylum Support Office (now European Union Agency for Asylum, EUAA)
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms
ECOWAS	Economic Community of West African States
ECtHR	European Court of Human Rights
ETM	Emergency Transit Mechanism
EUTF	EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa
GPSRIL	Guiding Principles on Shared Responsibility in International Law
GCR	UN Global Compact on Refugees
ICESCR	International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights
IBM	European Integrated Border Management
IOM	International Organisation for Migration
GCR	UN Global Compact on Refugees
ICCPR	International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights
ILC	International Law Commission
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
RSD	Refugee Status Determination
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UDHR	Universal Declaration of Human Rights
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The effectiveness of the UN Global Compact on Refugees (GCR) depends on increased cooperation among various parties for the protection of refugees. One interest the EU pursues through its collaboration with third states such as Türkiye, Tunisia, Serbia and Niger, and with international organisations such as UNHCR and IOM, is that of collectivised migration control. However such collaboration could lead to *excessive complexity*, making it difficult to discern the extent of each party's involvement and to attribute responsibility for wrongful acts. Where collaboration rests on *informal* arrangements, attributing responsibility becomes more challenging. Reduced accountability may be one of the reasons for engaging in such conduct. However, when the EU collaborates through third parties, progressive developments in the law of international responsibility increase the likelihood of the risk of encountering arguments on responsibility attribution that were previously inaccessible. It is these risks that the present report seeks to identify.

We have studied possible attribution arguments in the context of substandard protection and reception of migrants, including refugees, for cases related to all four countries. In so doing, our purpose was to identify arguable attribution arguments that the EU and other actors might risk being faced with. We found support for attribution arguments in various provisions of ARSIWA and ARIO for situations in Türkiye, Tunisia and Niger. While ILC articles did not provide a sufficient basis for attribution arguments in Serbia, such arguments could be based on Principle 7 GPSRIL.

We also examined the containment of refugee movements in cases related to all four countries. In the cases of Türkiye and Tunisia, attribution was subject to debate within the framework of the ILC articles. In the case of Niger, Principle 7 GPSRIL provided a means for establishing attribution alongside an argument based on a systemic approach. In the case of Serbia, the only available avenue for identifying an attribution argument was based on the systemic approach. In that category of cases, neither the ILC articles nor the GPSRIL provided a basis for establishing attribution.

In the cases of Serbia and Niger, we looked into attribution arguments related to human rights violations during border management operations. In the case of Serbia, we found that actions in which the EU is the principal actor were not attributable under the ILC articles. However, if the EU is regarded as a complicit actor, there may be room to argue for attribution under Article 14 ARIO.

For the cases of coproduction of refugee movements from Syria (related to our analysis of Türkiye) and from Libya (related to our analysis of Tunisia and Niger respectively), we found that it was possible to construct plausible arguments based on a systemic approach. However, neither ILC articles nor the GPSRIL provided a foundation for a convincing argument in this regard.

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The overarching conclusion drawn from all the country cases and categories in these countries is that the EU and its Member States are at a considerable risk of facing responsibility attribution arguments for violations of individual rights with these arguments being rooted in attribution norms found in the ILC articles or the GPSRIL. In its future third party collaborations on migration control and containment within or beyond the UN GCR framework, the EU and its Member States should take into consideration that the law of international responsibility has developed in ways that obliterate lacunae in attribution and continues to do so.

1. Introduction: what is the problem?

As matters stand, international migration and human rights law is a complex system bringing together different categories of actors. The UN Global Compact on Refugees (hereafter GCR) adds to the complexity. This has repercussions on the attribution of responsibility. At face value, GCR policy objectives seek to improve the lives of people on the move. But cooperation in the areas of migration and asylum is typically carried out to manage migration control in an environment where there are considerable power imbalances between actors. However, as a matter of principle, conduct that seeks to further GCR policy objectives may entail legally wrongful acts.

The very point of the GCR is to bring together actors and their resources to pursue GCR policy objectives, 'through the mobilisation of political will, a broadened base of support, and arrangements that facilitate more equitable, sustained and predictable contributions among States and other relevant stakeholders' (GCR C.7). The concept of 'other relevant stakeholders' is broad indeed, as suggested in a non-exhaustive list featuring in para A.3 GCR. This broadness is borne out in practice, as evidenced by the Report *Mapping the Field of Asylum and UNHCR GCR Actors* (Deliverable D2.2).

The GCR does not introduce any novel concepts in the realm of international relations when it brings together actors with diverse characteristics. Throughout modern history, European states and private actors have worked in tandem; a good example is the relationship between trading companies and governments when they use each other to pursue their objectives in the quest for colonial resources. In contemporary history, states have regularly sought to channel their strategic interests through international and non-governmental organisations. A survey of past decades in the migration and asylum policy field confirms this, with a growing number of IOs and NGOs offering themselves as conduits for resources and interests. In the course of that development, use has been made both of legally binding instruments and those which are not. What are the challenges for the attribution of international responsibility under such circumstances?

First, the plurality of actors involved in GCR implementation engenders the problem of *hypercomplexity*, resulting from a distribution of agency across actors with different organisational characteristics: states, governing structures within states, authorities, international organisations and private companies. In many cases, it would seem clear to a political scientist which actor wields major power in hypercomplex governance. For lawyers, such governance creates a great number of different legal relationships, making it difficult to disentangle jurisdictional limits, argue causality and to identify the most promising arguments for a meaningful attribution of legal responsibility¹.

¹ This is known as the problem of many hands in political science. See among others, Thompson, D. (1980), 'The moral responsibility of public officials: The problem of many hands', *American Political Science Review*, 74(4), p. 905–916; Wempe, J. F. D. B. (1998), *Market and Morality: Business Ethics and the Dirty and Many Hands Dilemma*, Amsterdam, Eburon; Mastop, R. (2010) 'Characterising responsibility in organisational structures: The problem of many hands', in Governatori, G. and Sartor, G. (eds.), *Deontic Logic in Computer Science*, 274–287, Berlin: Springer.

Second, the phenomenon of *informality* poses another problem for international lawyers. Arrangements that are not formally binding as a matter of international law, yet made in a manner stabilising expectations, are more challenging to capture in terms of responsibility norms. Informality engenders very complicated attribution arguments, marred by evidentiary issues.

The challenge, as we see it, is to identify an analytical framework that, i) enables a general analysis of legal, financial and political forms of responsibility; ii) specifically facilitates a discussion of responsibility attribution in the multi-actor environment of GCR implementation; iii) that is attentive to the risk of making primary rules ineffective; iv) the framework should enable an analysis of how the use of informal law-making could impact the feasibility of invoking international responsibility in legal contexts. Such a framework must take due account of ongoing debates in international law on responsibility attribution, including the perspective of actors in the Global South. One question that arises is what are the attribution arguments that the EU and other actors might encounter. We see our mission in this report to identify arguable attribution arguments, which does not necessarily mean that these arguments will be successful in a court of law or that we endorse their underlying assumptions from an ethical point of view.

We are mainly interested in legal responsibility, and this paper draws on the power and limits of legal argument. In the domain of international law, key for the understanding of human and migrants' rights, responsibility issues are broached by asking two questions: is there an internationally wrongful act, and is that act attributable to a state or an international organisation²? The first question, relating to wrongfulness, is primarily covered in ASILE D5.4. In the present text, we are mainly concerned with the second question of attribution, a question that connects well to deliverable D2.2., featuring a mapping of actors and networks relevant for GCR implementation. For attribution to be considered, it must be clear that the conduct in question is internationally wrongful and that no circumstances precluding wrongfulness exist³. These issues are beyond the scope of this report. As we will see, the question of attribution often entails discussions on causation and on the knowledge an actor had of the situation in question. At its core, the attribution of responsibility invariably confronts us with the relationship between primary rules of international law (such as the obligation not to engage in acts of *refoulement*) and secondary rules of international law (such as those regulating the attribution of legal responsibility for an act of *refoulement*). In simple terms, freedom from contradiction in the legal system would require that secondary rules do not reward the evasion of obligations accruing from primary rules.

² International Law Commission, 'Draft Articles on Responsibility of States for Internationally Wrongful Acts' *Yearbook of International Law Commission* 2001, Vol II (ARSIWA), Art. 2; International Law Commission, 'Draft Articles on the Responsibility of International Organizations for Internationally Wrongful Acts' *Yearbook of the International Law Commission* 2011, vol II (ARIO), art 4.

³ An argument that might emerge in the context of large-scale refugee movements is force majeure (Art. 23 ARSIWA and art. 23 ARIO). As force majeure precludes wrongfulness, it is not strictly speaking within the purview of a report focusing on attribution.

The attribution of legal responsibility is, ultimately, a matter of framing⁴. We consider it important that the discussion of legal attribution, in particular in the multi-actor field of GCR implementation, does not limit itself to the 2001 Articles on the Responsibility of States for Internationally Wrongful Acts (ARSIWA) and the 2011 Articles on the Responsibility of International Organizations (ARIO), articulated by the ILC. While the ILC enjoys considerable authority, it is evident that the Committee is not a lawmaker, and that its products cannot provide the ultimate answer to the question of what the law is⁵. During the years following the adoption of ARSIWA and ARIO respectively, much of the debate on international responsibility revolved around these two documents. Today, it has moved on, driven by new impulses, such as the 2020 Guiding Principles on Shared Responsibility in International Law (hereafter GPSRIL) and various critiques of the two ILC documents and of the GPSRIL. All these need to be considered, as we assess whether legal attribution arguments are arguable as matters stand today.

Those developments apart, the assumptions on which the secondary norms articulated by the ILC rest have been challenged in a fundamental way from Global South positions, questioning their neutrality. 'A TWAIL conception of state responsibility', B.S. Chimni explains, 'seeks a re-orientation of concepts, principles, rules, measures and remedies of rules of state responsibility to promote the value of justice in so far as it can be pursued through secondary rules.'⁶. As GCR implementation is a field where Northern and Southern interests diverge, it is likely that actors in the North, such as the EU and its Member States, will be faced with arguable claims on legal attribution, some of which stretch beyond the limited range of solutions available in the ILC articles. It is therefore advisable to map a broad array of conceivable argumentative strategies on legal attributability, making full use of the growing debates on attribution. These arguments will draw on the ILC ARSIWA and ARIO, on the GPSRIL and on the critiques directed at their content. This goes beyond arguments on the merits of restrictive or extensive interpretations of single second-order norms. Ongoing debates on the capability of international law to preserve injustice, in particular in the wake of decolonisation, and on the rootedness of responsibility norms in the era of high imperialism, suggest as much⁷.

⁴ On the critical importance of framing, see van Aaken, A. and Elm, J.P. (2021) 'Framing in and through Public International Law', in Andrea Bianchi, and Moshe Hirsch (eds), *International Law's Invisible Frames: Social Cognition and Knowledge Production in International Legal Processes*, Oxford: Academic, (<https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780192847539.003.0003>).

⁵ Azaria, D. (2020) 'Codification by Interpretation': The International Law Commission as an Interpreter of International Law' *European Journal of International Law*, vol. 31(1) p.171-200.

⁶ Chimni, B.S. (2021), 'The Articles on State Responsibility and the Guiding Principles of Shared Responsibility: A TWAIL Perspective', *European Journal of International Law*, Vol. 31 No. 4, 1–11, p. 1216.

⁷ Ibid p. 1213 and 1214; Hessbruegge, J. (2004), 'The Historical Development of the Doctrines of Attribution and Due Diligence in International Law', Vol. 36, No.4.

In Chapter 2, we distinguish political, financial and legal responsibility from each other and map the main norms of international law on responsibility attribution of relevance for GCR implementation in collaboration with actors in Türkiye, Tunisia, Serbia and Niger as the four countries of interest to this report⁸.

We introduce how mainstream articulations and interpretations of attribution norms have been challenged by novel rearticulations, including those by actors in the Global South. The four countries might not appear to be cases typically associated with GCR implementation, as the GCR is generally associated with cooperation in and with states in the vicinity of refugees' countries of origin. We expand that perspective to include responsibility attribution in the context of externalisation actors such as the EU.

Chapter 3 provides an overview table of the main attributability issues emerging in relation to the four countries of interest to this report. Chapter 4 addresses responsibility attribution related to the cooperation with Turkish actors. Chapter 5 does the same for Tunisia, Chapter 6 addresses Serbia and Chapter 7 relates to Niger. Chapter 8 offers conclusions.

⁸ For an overview of the issues raised in the four named countries, the reports of Work Package 5 may be consulted at <https://www.asileproject.eu/country-papers/>; Raach, F. and H. Sha'ath and T. Spijkerboer (2022) 'Country Report TUNISIA WP5', Country Reports No 55,65-66, ASILE (https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/D5.2_WP5-Tunisia-Country-Report-Final.pdf); See See Ovacık, G. and M. Ineli-Ciger, O. Ulusoy and T. Spijkerboer (2022) 'Country Report TÜRKİYE WP5. Country Reports', Country Report, ASILE (www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/D5.2_WP5-Türkiye-Country-Report-Final.pdf); Bachirou, A.T and A. Hamadou and T. Spijkerboer (2022) 'Country Report Niger WP5. Country Reports', p. 47, ASILE (http://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/D5.2_WP5-Niger-Country-Report-Final.pdf)

2. From political responsibility allocation in politics to responsibility attribution in international law

2.1 A typology of political, financial and legal responsibility

In our discussions with ASILE colleagues on the allocation of responsibility, three concepts have often recurred: legal responsibility, political responsibility and financial accountability. These terms are useful heuristic devices, permitting a first and tentative orientation in the complex mesh of agents, relations and responsibilities we are confronted with. We believe that political responsibility is a superior, all-encompassing category. Politics is the way a community expresses itself, and these articulations necessarily entail a dimension of political responsibility, ultimately exercised through the *pouvoir constituant*. Law and economic governance are special cases of politics, making legal responsibility and financial accountability into special cases of political responsibility. For that reason, legal responsibility is more limited than political responsibility, and we are moving from the broader term of responsibility *allocation* to the narrower term of legal *attribution*. Attribution is a term of art for the law of international responsibility and plays a central role as one of two elements of an internationally wrongful act in Article 2 ARSIWA. As Article 1 ARSIWA and Article 3 ARIO explain, every such act ‘entails the responsibility of’ the international actor to whom that act appertains. Indeed, the development of an attribution argument is pivotal for the implementation of international legal responsibility.

Evidently, the limit between legal attributability and mere political responsibility allocation is of critical interest in our context – a context where human and migrants’ rights are at stake. However, the attribution of legal responsibility to one actor or set of actors does not preclude that political responsibility is allocated as well. This could be an allocation to the same actor or set of actors, or to another actor or set of actors.

Let us consider an example from the field of financial accountability. As the EU is offering financial support to Serbia for border management (see Report on Serbia pp. 22, 28, 27), the EU will be accountable for making available these funds under relevant EU budget lines and following the relevant internal rules of the EU, including accounting rules. Apart from the conventional understanding of financial accountability, there exists a potential international legal responsibility for the influential effects of financial contributions that lead to internationally wrongful acts, violations of human rights law. Such an act could be attributable to the EU under Article 14 ARIO, without precluding potential attributability to Serbia under Article 19 ARIO. As we see, financial accountability and legal responsibility may, to some extent, exist in parallel with one another.

The same considerations apply to political responsibility, here understood as a form of responsibility resting on the actual or potential agreement of those actors affected by a conduct⁹. By way of example, the Western Balkans Route Leaders Statement of 2015 (see

⁹ This is an adapted version of Habermas’ discursive principle. Jürgen Habermas, *Faktizität und Geltung*, Suhrkamp, Frankfurt am Main, 1992, p. 138.

Report on Serbia p. 29) could raise issues of political responsibility to the extent that those affected by the Statement – citizens and non-citizens, refugees and non-refugees – hold the leaders behind the Statement to account in the political domain. This political responsibility is parallel to, and separable from, the attribution for any internationally wrongful act that the 2015 Statement might have contributed to – and thereby legal responsibility under international law. An analogous reasoning applies to the GCR *tout court*¹⁰.

2.2. Legal attribution in a multi-actor environment

How to attribute legal responsibility in the type of cooperation between different categories of actors envisaged by the GCR, a cooperation bringing together states, international organisations and non-state actors? We consider select norms on responsibility and attribution below and draw on commentaries and academic writing to shed light on their implications. We do not preclude that other norms might be relevant in single instances, but we believe that norms on complicity in the wide sense, as well as on circumvention are a baseline for any consideration of this question.

Any analysis of responsibility allocation will depend on the understanding with which we approach international law. As Aust has shown, there is no convincing story of progress, where a 'bilateralist' understanding of state responsibility gives way to one that foregrounds a community interest of sorts. Rather, he contends, 'both the constraints of bilateralism and the promises of the new, community-oriented international law appear to impact heavily on the issue of complicity'¹¹. To assess how indebted international responsibility norms still are to bilateralism today, suffice it to recall that the secondary norms of international responsibility are assumed to derive from primary norms that states have agreed to. Article 48 ARSIWA provides a concrete example of community orientation. It enables states other than the injured one to invoke responsibility, once the norm breached 'is established for the protection of the collective interest' of a group of states¹².

Aust points out that there is no primary rule making it illegal for states to aid and assist other states committing an internationally wrongful act, which leads to 'problems in grasping how the [ARSIWA] can provide for a rule on complicity'¹³ at all. Aust himself proposes an approach flowing from a principle of *abuse of rights*, and culminating in a rule of law argument implying that 'individual rights shall be exercised in a manner such that other legal subjects would incur no harm'¹⁴. His approach takes its cue, inter alia.

¹⁰ Gilbert, G. (2019) *Not bound but Committed: operationalising the Global Compact on Refugees*, International Migration, 57 (6). p.27-42.

¹¹ Aust, H. (2011), *Complicity and the Law of State Responsibility*, Cambridge University Press, p. 49.

¹² For an articulation of this approach, see the *Armed Activities on the Territory of the Congo* (Democratic Republic of the Congo v. Uganda): ICJ Judgment, 19 December 2005, (Separate Opinion of Judge Simma) para. 35.

¹³ Aust, H. (2011), *Complicity and the Law of State Responsibility*, Cambridge University Press, p. 69.

¹⁴ *Ibid*, p. 70. The focus on abuse obviously raises the problematic issue of intent, or bad faith, on the side of the complicit state. This issue, usually understood as a subjective criterion, connects

from Hersch Lauterpacht, who submitted that rights must not be used in a way that contravene international sociability ('action which is described as lawful may cease to be so if pursued in an unsocial manner')¹⁵. Aust is carefully tailoring the reach of his approach; he hedges against misunderstanding it to 'require the international legal system to include a certain rule on State complicity which is characterised by features A, B and C'¹⁶. Instead, 'a plausible case can be made that it will be necessary to find an answer in international law which responds to the problem of complicity... *How* international law responds ... is a matter of further examination in terms of positive law'¹⁷.

We find this convincing. Therefore, we reject an understanding that assumes the ILC ARSIWA and ARIO to be the sole valid baseline, and that relegates the GPSRIL, other commentary and critiques to aspirational status. To us, the lack of a foundational primary norm prohibiting complicity, or, for that matter, circumvention, means that *all* formulations of relevant secondary norms, whether originating within the ILCs work or not, may be critiqued for lacking a basis in primary law, and, hence, validity. The fact that the ICJ has ascribed the quality of customary international law to Article 16 ARSIWA does not detract from that argument¹⁸. It only brings home the point that questions of attribution are answered, be it the ICJ or any other actor, in an environment without stable foundational assumptions. As Aust has made clear, the problem of complicity is indeed one of the material completeness of international law¹⁹, and the challenge is for us to understand what 'completeness' might imply in the concrete contexts of GCR implementation. For this reason, we abstain from designating norms related to complicity, circumvention and related matters as either having a black letter law quality, or as being *de lege ferenda*.

That said, there is a practical reason separate out those approaches that are invested into the primacy of states and their bilateral relations from approaches that take their cue from the primacy of a totality. For the sake of reference in the following text, we use the term *formal approaches* to responsibility attribution as those approaches that are invested in the primacy of states in international law, and we term *systemic approaches* to responsibility attribution as those which are invested in the primacy of a totality, as

complicity to other areas of international law, as that of treaty interpretation to be done in good faith according to article 31.1 VCLT.

¹⁵ Ibid, Hersch Lauterpacht, as quoted by Aust on p. 66.

¹⁶ Ibid, p. 95.

¹⁷ Ibid. Emphasis in the original.

¹⁸ ICJ, *Application of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide Case (Bosnia and Herzegovina v Serbia and Montenegro) (Judgment)*, 217 para. 420. Lanovoy makes a number of observations that limit the value of the court's pronouncement with regard to art. 16 ARSIWA.

¹⁹ Aust, H. (2011), *Complicity and the Law of State Responsibility*, Cambridge University Press, p. 95.

Aust's international rule of law or Chimni's justice²⁰. The force field between both approaches is shaping concrete arguments on attribution.

We note that the GCR depends heavily on the existence of a collective body of actors. Therefore, it seems logical to subject it to a variety of attribution approaches, including those that emphasise the significance of this collective entity, when formulating arguments. The GPSRIL illustrate the views that open with a collective-based, systemic approach. The principles revolve around the shared responsibility for *indivisible* harm. This type of harm is differentiated from such harm that is divisible and therefore well covered by bilateralist readings of ARSIWA and ARIO. The GPSRIL Commentary explains:

An injury is divisible when contributions to that injury can be distinguished from each other by using a factual test of causation. This will be the case when an internationally wrongful act qualifies as the single necessary and sufficient cause of a certain injury: that injury would not have occurred but for the wrongful act (hence, it was necessary), and the wrongful act was sufficient on its own to bring about that injury. In such a situation, the international person committing that internationally wrongful act would not incur *shared* responsibility but *independent* international responsibility. Such independent responsibility would be established under the generally accepted rules of international responsibility²¹.

²⁰ A quote from Chimni's commentary on the GCR might illustrate what a formalist framing excludes:

'First, while the Refugee Compact, to its credit, addresses the problem of root causes of refugee flows, it fails to mention the responsibility of third States, in particular Western States, for recent outflows of refugees linked to their acts of intervention. To be sure, interventions alone are not responsible for refugee outflows. The State of origin is most often responsible, as for instance in the case of Rohingya refugees. The Refugee Compact therefore rightly notes that 'addressing root causes is the responsibility of countries at the origin of refugee movements' (para 8). But unfortunately, the Compact is silent on the role of external actors in the production of refugees. The major refugee outflows in recent years have been from Afghanistan, Iraq, Libya, and Syria, all of which have been the objects of armed intervention or responsibility-to-protect efforts of Western States. These interventions, often driven by objectives such as regime change, have been a humanitarian disaster. In other words, it is very often external social forces and States which aggravate local conflicts through intervention that are responsible for the mass exodus of refugees. Thousands of children like Aylan Kurdi die, not because of acts of omission and commission of the State of origin alone, but also because of the doings of third States.' BS Chimni (2019), 'Global Compact on Refugees: One Step Forward, Two Steps Back', *International Journal of Refugee Law* 630, Vol. 30, Issue 4, p. 1212.

²¹ Nollkaemper, A. and A. Jean, C. Ahlborn, B. Boutin, N. Nedeski and I. Plakokefalos with the collaboration of D. Jacobs (2020), 'Guiding Principles on Shared Responsibility in International Law', *European Journal of International Law*, Volume 31, Issue 1 (hereafter GPSRIL), principle 2, para 4, p. 24.

The concept of indivisible injury permits us to argue attribution in cases that we qualified as hypercomplex above. These are cases where individual contributions to an injury disappear in the fog of a collective action preceding it. In a way, the GPRSIL could be read as recovering lost ground for international responsibility: ground lost, because international conduct is increasingly distributed across different actors.

As a complement to the typology of political, financial and legal responsibility above, in Table 1 we set out some of the features associated with a formal or a systemic approach to arguing attributability. A formal style is slow to assume limitations to state freedom other than those that the state in question consented to, and circumscribes attributability from this vantage point. Its methodological register consists of a legal formalism resonating with the tradition of positivism. The interests promoted by these styles are those of states powerful enough to make or influence the primary and secondary rules of international law. Its temporal horizon is limited to the short and medium term, reflected, inter alia, in tropes as that of intertemporal law²². To exemplify, this would bar arguments from justice in international law that take their cue from the *longue durée* of colonialism.

At the other end of the arc, the presumption of a collective entity in international law informs arguments under a systemic approach to responsibility attribution. We have chosen to label it as systemic, as it refers to a greater whole, even as its referents are shifting – an international community, the completeness of law, or the justice in both. Methodologically, a range of approaches lend their support, stretching from liberal constitutionalism over an analysis of international law in history to Marxist thought or Third World Approaches to International Law (TWAIL). The perspective is informed by an international collective rather than that of the single sovereign, and its relation to history is transtemporal, letting demands on law accrue from the long view.

Table 1: Approaches to attribution

Approach to attribution	Methodological style	Type of interest promoted	Temporal aspect
Formal	Legal formalism	Interest of the individual state in freedom of action with limited legal responsibility	Short- to medium term; intertemporal

²² In international law, the concept of intertemporal law refers to the rule according to which, in Max Huber’s formulation, ‘a juridical fact must be appreciated in the light of the law contemporary with it, and not of the law in force at the time such a dispute in regard to it arises or falls to be settled’. Permanent Court of Arbitration, *Island of Palmas (Miangas)* 2 U.N. Rep. Int’l Arbitral Awards 829 (1928), p. 14.

Systemic	A range of disparate methods, including liberal constitutionalism, critiques of international law and the analysis of international law in history	Interest of a collective entity that includes states and other actors	<i>Longue durée</i> ; transtemporal
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Source: Auhor's elaboration.

2.3 To which type of actors can acts be attributed?

The ARSIWA assume that responsibility can be attributed to states as agents, while the ARIO assume that international organisations, and, in Part Five, even states, can be considered as agents to whom responsibility is attributable under it. The GPSRIL envisage attribution to international persons, a term that its Principle 1.a defines as covering states and international organisations. In the country analysis provided later in this report, we will see that it is indeed attributability to states and international organisations that is an issue. But the GCR context reaches further and involves the private sector to a considerable degree. As the GPSRIL Commentary points out, Principle 1.a does not prejudice 'the possibility that other actors, such as individuals or other non-state actors, bear international obligations and share responsibility in certain circumstances'²³. For Chimni, the GPSRIL remain nonetheless too closely tethered to the reductionist assumptions of ARSIWA and ARIO. He finds that the ARSIWA do 'not take into account the thick and structured relations between states and corporations in formulating the rule on attribution'²⁴. Should the GCR lead to public-private partnerships with problematic protection outcomes, the debate about the colonial legacies of states acting through private companies and their relevance to refugee law and policies would need to be intensified, in particular in the field of responsibility attribution.

According to the ILC Commentary on Article 14 ARIO, responsibility of an entity 'does not appear to depend on the nature and character of the entities concerned'. This begs the question of whether responsibility for complicity could be extended to other actors apart from states and international organisations, as private actors within the GCR framework. The comment could be construed as a cautious opening towards those who would like to see corporations included in the international legal regulation of responsibility.

²³ GPSRIL p 22, para. 1.

²⁴ BS Chimni (2019), 'Global Compact on Refugees: One Step Forward, Two Steps Back', International Journal of Refugee Law 630, Vol. 30, Issue 4; Guidelines, p. 1212.

2.4 Complicity

A suitable point of departure to track how international law addresses complicity in the commission of internationally wrongful acts is Article 16 ARSIWA:

A State which aids or assists another State in the commission of an internationally wrongful act by the latter is internationally responsible for doing so if:

- (a) that State does so with the knowledge of the circumstances of the internationally wrongful act; and
- (b) the act would be internationally wrongful if committed by that State.

Article 14 ARIIO offers a similar formulation for the responsibility of international organisations, while its article 58 adapts to address the responsibility of a state aiding or assisting in an act of an IO.

The GPSRIL focus on joint contributions to an indivisible injury. Its Principle 6 offers a take at the 'shared responsibility in situations of aid and assistance':

1. An international person shares responsibility when it knowingly aids or assists another international person in committing an internationally wrongful act, and the conduct of each of those international persons contributes to the indivisible injury of another person.
2. The requirement of knowledge in paragraph 1 is satisfied when an international person knew or should have known the circumstances of the internationally wrongful act.
3. An international person shares responsibility pursuant to paragraph 1 if the act would have been internationally wrongful if committed by that international person.

The GPSRIL Commentary explicitly names 'contributing to rendition schemes' and 'informing and facilitating interdiction at sea' as examples of such aid and assistance²⁵. Compared to that of the ARSIWA, the GPSRIL approach to complicity appears to alleviate evidentiary demands, as it is sufficient that an international person 'should have known the circumstances of an internationally wrongful act'. This is a reflection of the move by GPSRIL authors' towards a collectivist view of international responsibility. Then again, it should be acknowledged that discussions at the ILC during the first and second readings of ARSIWA were cognisant of the malleability of the subjective element, with ILC member Doudou Thiam expressly promoting that knowledge may be presumed²⁶. However, the difference between both approaches is less than dramatic once we consider that the term 'circumstances' as used by the ILC articles offers considerable latitude for interpretation, as do the terms 'to aid' and 'to assist'. If used to zoom out over a broader set of facts, all

²⁵ GPSRIL, at p. 41.

²⁶ Aust, H. (2011), *Complicity and the Law of State Responsibility*, Cambridge University Press, p. 233-4.

three terms can permit an interpreter to include such details whose exact understanding by the international actor in question remains in doubt, yet without operating with the deontological form of knowledge enabled by the GPSRIL perspective. In the end, the language of Article 16 ARSIWA and Article 14 ARIO can be interpreted in much the same way as that of Principle 6 GPSRIL.

The main characteristic of complicity is that it is ancillary in relation to a main act committed by another actor. This makes it different from other forms of indirect responsibility as direction, coercion, circumvention and joint and several responsibility²⁷. A first step in analysing a potential complicity situation is to identify that main, or principal, act and its internationally wrongful character. Once that is done, the door to establishing the responsibility of another actor for aiding or assisting in it opens. Once the principal act has been committed, complicity in that wrongful act of another becomes an autonomous wrongful act triggering responsibility in its own right²⁸.

As an example, consider the provision of Refugee Status Determination (RSD) by UNHCR in Tunisia. As explained in Chapter 4, there is no appeal avenue for UNHCR RSD, raising issues under the right to a remedy as guaranteed by human rights law. Tunisia has agreed to the presence of UNHCR and its provision of RSD on Tunisian territory. One line of argument would cast UNHCR's breach of the obligation to provide a remedy as the principal act, and the referral of asylum seekers by agents of the Tunisian state as a form of aid to UNHCR as the principal actor. As soon as UNHCR has rejected a refugee status application without an appeal option, the principal act has been committed, and complicity in that wrongful act of UNHCR becomes an autonomous wrongful act of Tunisia triggering responsibility for Tunisia²⁹. A second line of argument would be to cast Tunisia's general assent to UNHCR RSD without remedies on its territory as the principal act, with each single case of a breach being a form of aid by UNHCR triggering ancillary responsibility. This is a case where the conceptual force of the terms 'aid', 'assistance' and 'principal act' is not strong enough to clearly indicate who is aiding and who is aided.

²⁷ Lanovoy, V. (2015) 'Complicity', in *The Max Planck Encyclopedia of International Law* (opil.ouplaw.com/display/10.1093/law:epil/9780199231690/law-9780199231690-e2180), para 5.

²⁸ International law Commission, 'Draft Articles on Responsibility of States for Internationally Wrongful Acts, with commentaries' *Yearbook of International Law Commission* 2001, Vol II (ARSIWA), Commentary to Art. 16, ARSIWA, para. 1.

²⁹ Could Tunisia invoke the savings clause of article 58(2) ARIO, precluding responsibility 'as such' for an act by a member state of an international organisation carried out in accordance with the rules of that organisation? We do not think so. Tunisia's conclusion of a cooperation agreement between Tunisia and UNHCR is categorically different from Tunisia's contribution to acts of the UNHCR in its capacity as a UN Member State. Due to this categorical difference, Article 58(2) ARIO does not offer a means for Tunisia, or states in a comparable position, to avoid responsibility attribution.

Principle 7 of the GPSRIL on shared responsibility in situations of concerted action is a way to manage such complications. It is potentially relevant in the GCR context, as the principle concerns the participation in a course of conduct with a view to achieving agreed goals. Principle 7 reads as follows:

1. An international person shares responsibility when it knowingly acts in concert with another international person that commits an internationally wrongful act, and the conduct of each of those international persons contributes to the indivisible injury of another person.
2. International persons act in concert when each of them participates in a course of conduct with a view to achieving agreed goals.
3. The requirement of knowledge in paragraph 1 is satisfied when an international person knew or should have known the circumstances of the internationally wrongful act.
4. An international person shares responsibility pursuant to paragraph 1 if the act would have been internationally wrongful if committed by that international person.

As the commentary for Principle 7 states, '[t]he main rationale of shared responsibility for concerted action is that the injured party should not be put in a position of having to prove which parts of the injury are attributable to each of the responsible international persons'³⁰. For the injured party, the advantage of this principle is that it can confront each party participating in concerted action with claims for full compensation, adding an element of *obligatio in solidum* to the GPSRIL³¹. According to the GPSRIL commentary, the range of situations that Principle 7 would include, *inter alia*, the 'cooperation between the EU, its Member States and non-EU states in the context of migration controls and joint cross-border police activities'³². The commentary further points out a commonality for Principle 7 situations being that 'multiple actors coordinate their conduct with a view to achieving a common aim'.

2.5 Circumvention

Might hypercomplex or informal arrangements under the umbrella of the multi-actor and multi-jurisdictional GCR entail the *circumvention* of the law? In the language of international responsibility, circumvention is a technical term used to analyse normative losses brought about intentionally in interactions between states and international organisations. The ILC ARIO Commentary states that '[t]he term "circumvention" implies an intention on part of the international organisation to take advantage of the separate

³⁰ GSRIL, p. 45, para. 2.

³¹ While the ARSIWA do not contain a corresponding rule, it should be noted that this aspect of *obligatio in solidum* coheres with Art. 47.2.a ARSIWA.

³² Commentary to Principle 7 GPSRIL.

legal personality of its members³³. Compared to the requirement of knowledge under complicity provisions, this *mens rea* requirement comes with significant evidentiary hurdles. Allegations of circumvention may relate to a single instantiation of wrongful conduct as much as to systematic conduct, affecting a potentially large number of legal relations. In the field of individual rights, for example, an overall weakening of legal oversight increases the risk of rights violations, without necessarily being causally linked to individual violations being in evidence.

The ARIO address two constellations of circumvention. In the first one, an IO circumvents its own international obligations through decisions and authorisations addressed to members (Article 17):

1. An international organisation incurs international responsibility if it circumvents one of its international obligations by adopting a decision binding member states or international organisations to commit an act that would be internationally wrongful if committed by the former organisation.
2. An international organisation incurs international responsibility if it circumvents one of its international obligations by authorising member states or international organisations to commit an act that would be internationally wrongful if committed by the former organisation and the act in question is committed because of that authorisation.
3. Paragraphs 1 and 2 apply whether or not the act in question is internationally wrongful for the member states or international organisations to which the decision or authorisation is addressed.

In the second case, a member state of an international organisation circumvents its own obligations by instrumentalising an IO (Article 61):

1. A state member of an international organisation incurs international responsibility if, by taking advantage of the fact that the organisation has competence in relation to the subject-matter of one of the state's international obligations, it circumvents that obligation by causing the organisation to commit an act that, if committed by the state, would have constituted a breach of the obligation.
2. Paragraph 1 applies whether or not the act in question is internationally wrongful for the international organisation.

³³ International Law Commission, 'Draft Articles on the Responsibility of International Organizations for Internationally Wrongful Acts, with commentaries' *Yearbook of the International Law Commission* 2011, vol II, Commentary to art. 17 ARIO.

There are no corresponding provisions on circumvention in the ARSIWA. If, say, an EU Member State seeks to avoid its own obligations in international or EU law by acting through a non-EU state, attributability to that EU Member State needs to be analysed through rules on complicity or, as the case may be, direction and control.

As will emerge in the following chapters, we have not identified any case in the four countries considered in this report where circumvention appears to be *prima facie* arguable.

2.6 Implementation of international responsibility

International responsibility does not have consequences *eo ipso*. It needs to be invoked, and the question of who can lawfully invoke it is an important limiting factor. In contrast to the ARSIWA and the ARIO, the GPRSIL allow individuals, such as refugees, asylum seekers or migrants, to invoke responsibility by international actors. Principle 14.3 GPSRIL reads as follows:

An injured person that is not an international person is entitled to invoke the responsibility of each of the responsible international persons that share responsibility if the obligation breached is owed to that person individually.

The GPSRIL authors point out that this covers obligations owed to individuals, opening for invocations or responsibility for persons that have rights under human rights law.

This begs the question of whether mechanisms available in human rights law, such as treaty bodies or court proceedings, should be understood as *lex specialis* avenues that, once exhausted, *ipso facto* exhaust the entitlement to invoke responsibility under general international law on international responsibility. Once embraced, this restrictive interpretation would undo any value added by making the standing of individuals explicit, as done in the quoted principle. In the alternative, a reading emerges on the basis of Principle 14.3 GPSRIL that assumes a general right of individual invocation never fully consumed by using a treaty body or court proceedings.

ILC rules also provide for a plurality of responsible actors in a construction of joint and several responsibility. Article 47 ARSIWA states that '[w]here several states are responsible for the same internationally wrongful act, the responsibility of each state may be invoked in relation to that act. Article 48 ARIO extends this construction to the complicated relations of states and one or more IOs:

1. Where an international organisation and one or more States or other international organisations are responsible for the same internationally wrongful act, the responsibility of each State or organisation may be invoked in relation to that act.
2. Subsidiary responsibility may be invoked insofar as the invocation of the primary responsibility has not led to reparation.

...

Article 41 ARSIWA and Article 42 ARIO address the consequences of serious breaches of peremptory norms of international law for the implementation of responsibility, imposing an obligation to 'cooperate to bring to an end through lawful means any serious breach'

(para. 1 of each article). Also, no state or IO shall ‘recognise as lawful a situation created by a serious breach within the meaning of Article 41, nor render aid or assistance in maintaining that situation’. Principle 13 GPSRIL largely mirrors these provisions, adding obligations for IOs in relation to serious breaches of peremptory norms by states. Article 40(2) ARSIWA and Article 41(2) ARIO define a breach as serious ‘if it involves a gross or systematic failure by the responsible State to fulfil the obligation’.

These implementation rules could be relevant for situations such as the pushbacks of migrants and asylum seekers to Libya, where the use of violence possibly amounting to torture has been reported to take place in militia-run detention centres³⁴. However, given the limitations of the ARSIWA and ARIO, state and IO complicity in pushbacks presupposes that there is a link between pushbacks and the occurrence of systematic rights violations carried out by non-state actors. Nonetheless, in situations where no such link exists, relevant international actors still have the obligation to bring to an end with lawful means serious breaches in detention centres.

Articles 17 and 61 ARIO reduce the community interests of international law to a narrow set-up of peremptory norms, adding a requirement that breaching them is also considered serious. . As Chimni points out, the Committee ‘did not consider the possibility of the emergence, or progressive development, of positive peremptory obligations, which would have called for framing secondary rules that advanced the values of solidarity and justice’³⁵.

3. Overview of main attribution cases

For ease of reference, we add a table listing the main cases for each of the four countries where the attribution of legal responsibility is arguable under international law. The argument on each of these cases is set out in the country-specific chapters below.

Table 2: Main Attribution Cases

Case	Actor	Attribution argument drawing on
Türkiye		
Substandard protection and reception of migrants, including refugees, in Türkiye	Türkiye	Art. 4 ARSIWA

³⁴ In 2021, a detention centre was opened and controlled by a militia that reportedly extorts detained migrants and treats them in violation of human rights. Creta, S. (2021), ‘Libya’s detention centre closures: lancing lawlessness or consolidating political control?’ Euronews <<https://www.euronews.com/2021/07/30/a-hotbed-of-squalor-and-torture-libya-is-closing-its-migrant-detention-centres>>.

³⁵ Chimni, B.S. (2021), ‘The Articles on State Responsibility and the Guiding Principles of Shared Responsibility: A TWAIL Perspective’, *European Journal of International Law*, Vol. XX No. XX, 1–11, p 1217.

and Greece, as a consequence of the EU-TR Statement	Greece EU Member States	Art.4 ARSIWA Art. 16 ARSIWA Principle 7 GPSRIL
Containment of primary movements from Syria and of secondary movements from Türkiye	Türkiye EU Member States	Art 4.ARSIWA Art. 16 ARSIWA Principle 7 GPSRIL Attributable under systemic approach arguments
Coproduction of refugee movements from Syria	France, the Netherlands as examples of EU Member States EU	Systemic approach arguments Attributable under systemic approach arguments
Tunisia		
Substandard protection and reception of migrants, including refugees, in Tunisia	UNHCR (principal actor) Tunisia (complicit actor) Tunisia (principal actor) UNHCR (complicit actor)	Art. 6 ARIO Art. 58 ARIO Art. 4 ARSIWA Art. 14 ARIO
Containment of refugee movements from Tunisia	Tunisia EU ICMPD Member States of either organisation	Art. 4 ARSIWA Art. 6 ARIO Art. 6 ARIO Art. 58 ARIO Attributable under systemic approach arguments
Coproduction of refugee movements from Libya	European states who contributed to the military conflict in Libya	Attributable under systemic approach arguments
Serbia		
Substandard protection and reception of migrants, including refugees, in Serbia	Serbia EU EU shared with Serbia and individual EU Member States	Art. 4 ARSIWA Not attributable under ILC articles Principle 7 GPSRIL

Human rights violations in the course of border management in Serbia	Serbia EU through Frontex (principal actor) EU (complicit actor)	Art. 4 ARSIWA Not attributable to Frontex under ILC articles Art. 6 and 14 ARIO
Containment of refugee movements in Serbia	Serbia EU EU shared with Serbia and EU Member States	Art. 4 ARSIWA Not attributable under ILC articles Attributable under Principle 7 GPSRIL Attributable under systemic approach arguments
Niger		
Substandard protection and reception of migrants, including refugees, in Niger	Niger UNHCR (in complicity with Niger) EU EU shared with Niger, the UNHCR, and resettlement countries	Art. 4 ARSIWA Art. 6 and 14 ARIO Not attributable under ILC articles Attributable under Principle 7 GPSRIL
Human rights violations in the course of border management in Niger	Niger EU and individual EU Member States (complicit actors)	Art. 4 ARSIWA Art. 14 ARIO and Art.16 ARSIWA Principle 7 GPSRIL
Containment of refugee movements in Niger	Niger EU	Art 4 ARSIWA Not attributable under ILC articles Attributable under systemic approach arguments
Coproduction of refugee movements from Libya	European states who contributed to the military conflict in Libya	Attributable under systemic approach arguments

Source: Authors' elaboration

4. Türkiye

4.1. CASE 1: Formal responsibility with respect to substandard protection and reception in Türkiye and Greece

4.1.1. Wrongful act

The wrongful acts identified in this case of formal responsibility attribution consist of human rights violations arising from the substandard protection and reception of migrants and refugees in Türkiye and in Greece that take place in the course of implementing the EU-Türkiye Statement. These acts are wrongful as they violate international legal obligations of Türkiye and Greece enshrined in the Refugee Convention, ICCPR and ECHR as well as Greek obligations under relevant norms of the EU *acquis* and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights³⁶.

4.1.2. Causation

The main cause of the wrongful acts originates from already existing shortcomings of the reception and asylum systems of these countries which further deteriorated after the EU-Türkiye Statement. The ASILE Country Report on Türkiye sums up this situation by making reference to Türkiye's geographical limitation to the Refugee Convention, existing shortcomings in the Turkish asylum system and the overburdening of the Turkish capacity for hosting refugees, which all make returns to Türkiye under the EU-Türkiye Statement questionable under international law³⁷.

The effective implementation of the Statement rests on the assumption that Türkiye is a safe third country to which asylum seekers can be returned by EU States. Thus, their asylum applications are considered inadmissible and not assessed on their merit in Greece. Whether Türkiye can be accepted as a safe third country under EU law standards is controversial given its geographic limitation to the Refugee Convention and shortcomings in the Turkish asylum system, especially in the context of right to an effective remedy and principle of *non-refoulement*. Türkiye's capacity to offer dignified

³⁶ Secondary EU law has a place within international responsibility analysis because its violation entails violation of primary EU law, namely, the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU and Treaty on EU, that bring the obligation to Member States to comply with EU secondary law. Whereas from the perspective of justiciability, EU mechanisms would supersede in practice for ensuring compliance with EU law, in terms of establishing the chain of causation for international legal responsibility, binding legal obligations emanating from EU law are still relevant.

³⁷ See Ovacık, G. and M. Ineli-Ciger, O. Ulusoy and T. Spijkerboer (2022) 'Country Report TÜRKİYE WP5. Country Reports', Country Report, ASILE (www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/D5.2_WP5-Türkiye-Country-Report-Final.pdf) (hereinafter TÜRKİYE Report).

standards of living and effective international protection to the almost four million asylum seekers that it is currently hosting remains doubtful³⁸.

Türkiye's geographical limitation to the Refugee Convention does not constitute a wrongful act in itself. However, its implications on the ground create an environment conducive to human rights violations. The impacts are twofold: First, on a theoretical level, as a result of the geographical limitation, non-European asylum seekers whose international protection applications are subject to individual assessment in Türkiye are eligible to obtain conditional refugee status which allows them to legally stay in Türkiye until repatriation or resettlement becomes possible. This is a national legal status – as opposed to the refugee status under the Refugee Convention, and thus by definition devoid of the guarantees of international refugee law, and that in certain aspects undercuts the rights under the Refugee Convention. Syrian refugees are also outside the scope of the Refugee Convention as without being subject to individual assessment, they are categorically granted temporary protection which is also a national legal status. Second, on a practical level, conditional refugees have a disadvantageous position compared to conventional refugees in terms of access to labour market and travel documentation and these challenges are magnified with the trend. Similar challenges also appear for Syrian refugees in access to labour market, travel documentation and resettlement³⁹. Also, decrease in quotas for resettlement offered by third countries means slimmer chances of resettlement which translate into prolonged stay in Türkiye⁴⁰.

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- ³⁸ TÜRKİYE Report 41–42; Ovacık, G. (2021) *Turkish Judicial Practices on International Protection, Removal and Administrative Detention in Connection with the Safe Third Country Concept*, On İki Levha Publications, p. 72–75; Danish Council for Refugees and European Council on Refugees and Exiles (2016), 'Desk Research on Application of a Safe Third Country and a First Country of Asylum Concepts to Turkey'; Peers, S. and R. Emanuela (2016), 'EU Law Analysis: The EU, Turkey and the Refugee Crisis: What Could Possibly Go Wrong?', EU Law Analysis Blog, <eulawanalysis.blogspot.com/2016/02/the-eu-turkey-and-refugee-crisis-what.html>; Lehner, R. (2018) 'The EU-Turkey Deal: Legal Challenges and Pitfalls', International Migration, Vol. 57, Issue 2 p.176-185; Poon, J. (2016) 'EU-Turkey Deal: Violation of, or Consistency with, International Law?', European Papers Vol. 1 No. 3; Ovacık, G. (2020) 'Compatibility of the Safe Third Country Concept with International Refugee Law and Its Application to Turkey', Perceptions Journal of International Affairs Vol. XXV Number 1, p. 61-80; Şimşek, D. (2017), 'Turkey as a "Safe Third Country"? The Impacts of the EU-Turkey Statement on Syrian Refugees in Turkey', Perceptions Journal of International Affairs, Vol. 22, No. 4, p. 161-182; Turan, Y and Osman Ş. (2017), *AB'ye İltica Başvurularının Değerlendirilmesinde Geri Kabul ve Güvenli Üçüncü Ülke Tartışmaları*, 3 PESA International Journal of Social Studies 47; Esen, A. (2018), *Avrupa Birliği Mevzuatında Güvenli Üçüncü Ülke Kavramı ve Türkiye-AB Geri Kabul Anlaşmasına Yansımaları*, 38 Public and Private International Law Bulletin 11.
- ³⁹ Erdoğan, M.M. (2020) *Syrians in Turkey: A Framework for Achieving Social Cohesion with Syrians in Turkey*, p. 17-26.
- ⁴⁰ Ergin, A.D and Y. Kader (2021) 'On the Difference That Turkey's Geographical Limitation to the 1951 Convention Makes in the Protection of Non-European Refugees - Refugee Law Initiative Blog', <https://rli.blogs.sas.ac.uk/2021/06/22/on-the-difference-that-Turkeys-geographical-limitation-to-the-1951-convention-makes-in-the-protection-of-non-european-refugees/>.

The shortcomings of the Turkish asylum system are related to Türkiye being the top refugee hosting country in the world. Also, the newly administered reforms in the asylum system and legislation had to be tested with the largest refugee influx in the country's history. Deficiencies concerning delays in asylum processes and difficulties in accessing rights and services were reported.⁴¹. Mainly initiated throughout the EU accession process, Türkiye implemented legislative, institutional and policy reforms related to asylum and began making gradual changes to align its asylum and migration structures to the EU framework. The EU and its Member States granted extensive technical and financial support to those reforms. Although the groundwork was laid in earlier years, the reforms largely became effective after the Syrian influx into Türkiye started in 2011. Apart from challenges in practice arising from the implementation of the new framework, legislative developments in the removal regime that occurred between 2016 and -2019 also caused rights violations. Legislative amendments which are still in effect today brought a new basis for of removal due to a person's connection to terrorist activities and potentially subjected asylum seekers and refugees to removal based on national security and public order reasons. A legislative amendment removing automatic suspensive effect of judicial complaint against removal orders remained in effect for almost three years before being cancelled for being found in violation of right to an effective remedy. This entailed removal practices targeting foreigners including asylum seekers and refugees without judicial assessment of risk of *refoulement*.⁴². The EU-Türkiye Statement was executed and implemented against this background in Türkiye. When an asylum seeker is returned to Türkiye under EU-Türkiye Statement or is deterred from leaving Türkiye due to prospect of being returned under EU-Türkiye Statement, these are the conditions these conditions create circumstances that can lead to human rights violations for the asylum seeker.that the asylum seeker faces that are conducive to human rights violations.

At the outset of the Syrian Civil War, the Greek islands received a major influx of asylum seekers who wanted to continue their journey further from Türkiye towards Europe. In response to this influx and in view of the implementation of the EU-Türkiye Statement, a hotspot approach was adopted in the Greek islands whereby the incoming asylum seekers were contained in the islands without being allowed passage to the mainland. In parallel to its impact in Türkiye, the EU-Türkiye Statement resulted in an immediate deterioration

⁴¹ Ergin, A.D. and Y. Kader (2021), 'On the Difference That Turkey's Geographical Limitation to the 1951 Convention Makes in the Protection of Non-European Refugees - Refugee Law Initiative Blog', (<https://rli.blogs.sas.ac.uk/2021/06/22/on-the-difference-that-turkeys-geographical-limitation-to-the-1951-convention-makes-in-the-protection-of-non-european-refugees/>); Ovacık, G. (2020), 'Turkish Judiciary's Interpretation of "Risk of Absconding" as a Ground for Detention for the Purpose of Removal', Nijmegen Migration Law Working Papers; Ovacık, G. (2021), 'Compensation for Unlawful Practices Related to Administrative Detention of Foreigners in Turkey', Vol. 41 Public and Private International Law Bulletin; Ovacık, G. (2020), "Türk Anayasa Mahkemesi'nin İçtihadı Işığında Sınır Dışı Kararlarına Karşı Yargısal İtirazın Hukuki Etkisi", Marmara Üniversitesi Hukuk Fakültesi Hukuk Araştırmaları Dergisi 1047; Ovacık, G. (2020) "A Judicial Review of the De Facto Detention of Foreigners in Turkey", *Border Crossing*, Vol. 10, No. 2, p. 143.

⁴² Ovacık, G. (2021) 'Turkish Judicial Practices on International Protection, Removal and Administrative Detention in Connection with the Safe Third Country Concept' On İki Levha Publications, p. 163–166.

of the human rights standards on the Greek islands due to the hotspot approach, especially in terms of the prohibition of inhuman and degrading treatment as enshrined in Article 3 of ECHR and Article 7 of ICCPR and the right to liberty and security as enshrined in Article 5 of ECHR and Article 9 of ICCPR⁴³. The implementation of the EU-Türkiye Statement resulted in a different processing procedure of those arriving at Greek islands from Türkiye as compared to other asylum seekers arriving in Greece. Whereas they would otherwise enter into the Greek asylum system, they were accommodated for prolonged periods and under detrimental conditions in the hotspots without their asylum applications being considered. Routine detention practices and deterioration of detention conditions including problems in access to and delays in asylum procedures, challenges with interpretation and legal assistance were the main problems that also undermined Greek compliance with the Asylum Procedures Directive⁴⁴. These problems have increased significantly due to the fact that very few returns were in fact carried out under the EU-Türkiye Statement⁴⁵. The EU-Türkiye Statement rests on the premise that Türkiye and Greece assume the gate-keeping role and prevent the influx towards the rest of Europe. Thus, regardless of the changing trends in the volume and direction of the movement of Syrian refugees between these two countries, the Statement envisages that the influx is contained in this region. This establishes the axis of correlation between the Statement and deterioration of conditions in Türkiye and Greece.

4.1.3. Responsibility attribution

Attribution of responsibility to Türkiye and Greece

As the operation of the asylum system in Türkiye and Greece rests with the executive organs of these states, the wrongful acts committed in the course of their functioning are attributable to these states under Article 4 ARSIWA. The chain of causation is straightforward in case of breaches of the Refugee Convention, ICCPR and ECHR by Türkiye and Greece, as well as relevant EU acquis norms and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights by Greece, as applicable. Türkiye and Greece are the principal actors involved in the breaches making the wrongfulness of the conduct attributable to them and triggering their legal responsibility under ARSIWA. Based on this causal relationship, Article 12 ARSIWA on the existence of a breach of an international obligation and Article 13 ARSIWA on international obligation in force for a state come into play. Therefore, Türkiye and Greece, have not acted in conformity with their human rights obligations, in particular those prohibiting inhuman and degrading treatment and enshrining the right to liberty and security. These rights are laid down in the instruments mentioned above, and both states were bound by these acts at the time the different violations of rights occurred.

⁴³ TÜRKİYE Report 4.

⁴⁴ TÜRKİYE Report 42–43.

⁴⁵ Kienast J, Tan NF and Vedsted-Hansen J, 'Human Rights Compatibility & Attribution of Responsibility', p 42-43.

Attribution of responsibility to the EU and its Member States

Having established the causation link for Türkiye and Greece as the principal actors, the role of the EU and EU Member States with respect to the wrongful acts in question needs to be considered. As outlined in the causation section above, the implementation of the EU-Türkiye Statement occurred against the background of violations of human rights obligations by Türkiye and Greece. These violations are arguably exacerbated by the increasing pressure on both asylum systems through the Statement. The latter has an indirect impact on the mobility routes and schemes of asylum seekers as it purports to prevent irregular movements. Additionally, the EU-Türkiye Statement also came with a financial component (the Facility for Refugees in Türkiye) with a total budget of EUR 6 billion. This support was intended to provide humanitarian and development assistance as well as capacity enhancement in managing the irregular migration⁴⁶. The attribution of responsibility to EU Member States⁴⁷ based on the violations by Türkiye and Greece therefore appears as arguable. The legal scheme of responsibility issues in connection with this involvement may be formulated based on the ARSIWA and GPSRIL.

Article 16 ARSIWA on aid and assistance in the commission of an internationally wrongful act regulates international responsibility of a state aiding or assisting another state in committing an internationally wrongful act. Principle 7 GPSRIL on shared responsibility in situations of concerted action states that an international person, meaning a state or international organisation, shares responsibility when each of them participates in a course of conduct with a view to achieving agreed goals in commission of an internationally wrongful act.

The international responsibility for aid and assistance under ARSIWA and shared responsibility for concerted action under GPSRIL rest on parallel conditions. Under ARSIWA, responsibility arises as long as the aiding and assisting state has knowledge of the circumstances of the internationally wrongful act, the aid or assistance has the purpose and consequence of facilitating the commission of the wrongful act and the act would be internationally wrongful if committed by the aiding and assisting state⁴⁸. Under the GPSRIL, responsibility is triggered when the international person that takes part in concerted action has knowledge of the circumstances of the internationally wrongful act, the conduct contributes to the indivisible injury of another person and the act would be internationally wrongful if committed by the international person taking part in the concerted action⁴⁹.

⁴⁶ TÜRKİYE Report p.26–29.

⁴⁷ Despite much evidence and legal arguments to the contrary, by virtue of *NF v European Council* [2017] General Court of the European Union T-192/16; *NG v European Council* [2017] General Court of the European Union T-193/16; *NM v European Council* [2017] General Court of the European Union T-257/16 the executors are accepted as the EU member states and not the EU itself. Accepting these judgments in their face value for the sake of moving forward with the argument here, makes ARSIWA applicable rather than ARIIO.

⁴⁸ ARSIWA, Article 16, commentary (2-6).

⁴⁹ GPSRIL, Principle 7, commentary (6-10).

In the case of aid and assistance, the ARSIWA Commentary outlines that international legal responsibility arising from aid and assistance is of a derivative nature, why the primary responsibility rests with Türkiye and Greece, whereas secondary responsibility of EU Member States based on their supporting role is triggered to the extent that the EU-Türkiye Statement contributed to the human rights violations.

This framework accommodates a legal construction where EU Member States are involved in the human rights violations in Türkiye and Greece by aid and assistance or concerted action through the EU-Türkiye Statement.

As to the first condition of knowledge of the circumstances of the internationally wrongful act, the ARSIWA Commentary recognises that, normally, when a state provides material or financial assistance or aid to another state, it does not assume the risk that such assistance or aid may be used to carry out an internationally wrongful act. In order for the aiding and assisting state to bear international responsibility it should be aware of the circumstances in which its aid or assistance is intended to be used by the other state⁵⁰. The GPSRIL have a lower threshold as to the requirement of knowledge as it recognises, in addition to actual knowledge, the cases of constructed knowledge where the international person should have known the circumstances of the internationally wrongful act⁵¹. The GPSRIL soften the mental element that is required for the responsibility for aid or assistance⁵². It is notable that ECtHR also considers constructed knowledge to be sufficient and does not require actual knowledge for finding a violation of Article 3 of ECHR in case of transfers of asylum seekers⁵³. The EU Annual Reports on Türkiye before the execution of the EU-Türkiye Statement acknowledge the shortcomings on the ground regarding protection and access to rights and services by asylum seekers and refugees. For example, the 2015 Türkiye Report⁵⁴ acknowledges the shortcomings in the asylum system as follows:

'Despite commendable efforts by the authorities, around 500 000 refugee children have no access to education. Refugees living outside the camps still face difficult living conditions and considerable challenges in accessing essential services. Some 80 satellite cities across Türkiye are part of the national hosting system for non-Syrian refugees. Their reception capacity to provide decent living conditions and access to basic services differs from city to city but is generally limited. This has put local capacity and resources under significant strain in many places. [...] Incidents where Türkiye did not respect the principle of 'non-refoulement' were reported and criticised by civil society.'

⁵⁰ ARSIWA, Article 16, commentary (4); Lanovoy, V. (2022), 'Complicity', Max Planck Encyclopedia on International Law, para 21.

⁵¹ GPSRIL, Principle 7, commentary (9)

⁵² Lanovoy, V.(2020), 'The Guiding Principles on Shared Responsibility in International Law: Too Much or Too Little?', 31, *European Journal of International Law*, Vol. 31, Issue 1, p. 15–72, 1235.

⁵³ ECtHR, *M.S.S. v. Belgium and Greece*, Appl. no. 30696/09, Judgment of 21 January 2011 para ,358.

⁵⁴ European Commission (2015), 'Türkiye 2015 Report', SWD, 216 final 70.

There is a perceptible shift in this critical discourse after the EU-Türkiye Statement. This is probably due to the political motivation to make the Statement work, rather than to any improvement of conditions in Türkiye. In any case, there is sufficient evidence to argue that the EU was aware of the deficiencies in the Turkish asylum system that amounted to internationally wrongful acts at the time of entering into the Statement.

As to the condition of purpose and consequence of facilitation of the wrongful act in the context of the ARSIWA or of contribution to indivisible injury in terms of the GPSRIL, it should be noted that the threshold described for concerted action is accepted to be lower than the cases of aid and assistance⁵⁵.

Whereas the cooperation with Türkiye under the EU-Türkiye Statement contributed to the improvement of protection and reception standards for asylum seekers, it nevertheless triggers attribution of international responsibility, because the containment of asylum seekers translated into greater numbers of asylum seekers being subjected to these conditions. While the resettlement component of the EU-Türkiye Statement does create a mobility scheme, it is tied to returns to Türkiye and limited to Syrians who have not attempted irregular passage to Europe. Furthermore, the statistics show that the impact of this contained mobility scheme is minimal; there are nearly 3.5 million Syrians under temporary protection in Türkiye, while the total number of Syrians resettled to European countries under the EU-Türkiye Statement remains at less than 40 000 persons⁵⁶. Admittedly, the deficiencies in the asylum systems of Türkiye and Greece existed before the EU-Türkiye Statement. However, at least a part of the relevant group of asylum seekers faced them while being contained in Türkiye as a consequence of the EU-Türkiye Statement.

⁵⁵ Murray, O. (2020), 'Liability *In Solidum* in the Law of International Responsibility: A Comment on Guiding Principle 7', *European Journal of International Law*, Vol. 31, Issue 4, p.1249, 1257.

⁵⁶ According to the official statistics of the Turkish Presidency of Migration Management updated as of 1 June 2023, (<https://en.goc.gov.tr/temporary-protection27>).

This meant that many more asylum seekers were subjected to somewhat improved⁵⁷, but still overall detrimental conditions in Türkiye and Greece⁵⁸. If we are to accept the findings of the EU that the number of irregular sea passages from Türkiye to Greece is successfully achieved by the Statement⁵⁹, it follows that if it was not for the Statement, the number of asylum seekers who would be dispersed to other EU Member States would be relatively higher. Arguably, this would mean overall better standards of protection without too much overburdening of asylum systems in only a few countries. Although this would not guarantee that there would be no rights violations at all, it would still create a relatively less conducive environment.

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- ⁵⁷ A simple comparison of EU and Turkish funds mobilised for protection of Syrian refugees gives an idea of the magnitude of the needs in Turkey and the inadequacy of the new EU funds to alleviate them. EU funds committed under EU-Turkey Statement amount to EUR 6 billion, and negotiations for a further EUR 3 billion are continuing. There has been much controversy around the exact cost of Syrian refugee relief on Turkish national budget and varying statements by Turkish Deputy Prime Minister point to USD 30 billion by 2018 (<https://www.aa.com.tr/tr/ekonomi/basbakan-yardimcisi-akdag-suriyeliler-icin-harcanan-toplam-maliyet-84-milyar-880-milyon-lira/990509>) and USD 7.6 billion by 2016 (https://www.huffpost.com/entry/turkey-syrian-refugees_n_55fbd728e4b08820d9183073). In his very much contested statement while addressing the Global Refugee Forum, Turkish President Erdoğan claimed that 40 billion USD was spent by 2020 (<https://www.tccb.gov.tr/konusmalar/353/113993/kuresel-multeci-forumu-nda-yaptiklari-konusma>). According to Turkish Presidency Annual Programs, the humanitarian aid provided to Syrians in Turkey was 7.2 billion USD in 2019, 6.7 billion USD in 2018, 5.85 billion USD in 2016, 1.6 billion USD in 2014 and 1.57 billion USD in 2013 (Turkish Presidency Annual Programs are available at <https://www.sbb.gov.tr/yillik-programlar/>). In any case EU funds appear to be at best a job half done and it is not possible to argue that EU support covered the deficiencies suffered by Turkish asylum system.
- ⁵⁸ Human rights impact of the EU-Turkey Statement has been subject to extensive criticism in Work, S. (2018), 'The EU-Turkey Deal: A Legal Analysis: Is the Deal in Compliance with Refugee Law and Human Rights Law?', IRL Research Paper; 'A Blueprint for Despair: Human Rights Impact of the EU-Turkey Deal' (Amnesty International 2017); Ulusoy, O. and H. Battjes (2017), 'Situation of Readmitted Migrants and Refugees from Greece to Turkey under the EU-Turkey Statement', 15; Ergin, A.D. (2020), 'What Happened at the Greece-Turkey Border in early 2020?', Verfassungsblog, (<https://verfassungsblog.de/what-happened-at-the-greece-turkey-border-in-early-2020/>); Şimşek, D. (2017), 'Turkey as a "Safe Third Country"? The Impacts of the EU-Turkey Statement on Syrian Refugees in Turkey', Perceptions Journal of International Affairs, Vol. 22, No. 4, p. 169-173; Koca (2015), 'Deconstructing Turkey's "Open Door" Policy towards Refugees from Syria' Migration Letters, 12(3), p. 218.
- ⁵⁹ European Commission (2016), 'Managing the Refugee Crisis: Commission Reports on Progress Made in the Implementation of the EU-Turkey Statement' (https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_16_2181). For the opposing view see; Spijkerboer, T. (2016), 'Fact Check: Did the EU-Turkey Deal Bring Down the Number of Migrants and of Border Deaths?', (<https://blogs.law.ox.ac.uk/research-subject-groups/centre-criminology/centreborder-criminologies/blog/2016/09/fact-check-did-eu#:~:text=On%20March%2018th%2C%202016%2C%20the,the%20number%20of%20border%20deaths.>)

The third condition (the act qualifying as internationally wrongful if committed by the aiding and assisting state) is quite straightforward, as the provision of material aid to a state that uses the aid to commit human rights violations is an explicit example cited in the ARSIWA Commentary⁶⁰. Principle 7 GPSRIL also provides for this opposability requirement⁶¹. The Refugee Convention, the ICCPR and ECHR and, where applicable, the relevant EU acquis and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, the violation of which constitutes the basis for the internationally wrongful acts, are binding for EU Member States. Because the direct violation of an obligation contained in these instruments by an EU Member State would constitute an internationally wrongful act, an EU Member State cannot aid and assist other states in their violations of an obligation contained in these instruments.

The EU-Türkiye Statement aimed at containing asylum seekers from Syria in Türkiye by decreasing their ability to move from Türkiye to EU Member States and by returning those who have crossed irregularly through Türkiye. Whether intentionally or not, the EU was clearly involved in the exposure of the asylum seekers to rights violations. Assistance or concerted action demonstrated through cooperation under the EU-Türkiye Statement results in asylum seekers being subjected to detrimental conditions, conditions that EU Member States would be prevented from lawfully imposing on them if those asylum seekers were present in their own territory. This may constitute the evasion of international obligations by working with or through others⁶².

This situation is specifically elaborated in the GPSRIL Commentary with a focus on conditions in Greece. The text provides that, in order for international responsibility to be triggered, the goal of the concerted action in itself does not have to be unlawful, and it is sufficient for wrongful acts to have been committed in the course of the concerted action, nevertheless. As such, the declared purposes of the EU-Türkiye Statement that are to prevent irregular migration and smuggling are not in themselves in contravention of international law. However, the Statement included the return of irregular migrants passing to Greece from Türkiye,

*'at a time when it was well known that detention conditions in Greece and deficiencies in its asylum procedure were in violation of the ECHR. The implementation of the above action point in the EU-Türkiye Statement put further pressure on the already overburdened Greek asylum system, and various reports indicated that the Greek asylum system remained deficient, and refugees and migrants in camps were exposed to inhumane conditions. Accordingly, this is an example of multiple international persons pursuing an agreed goal through concerted action that is itself lawful, but during which one or multiple wrongful acts may have been committed'*⁶³.

⁶⁰ ARSIWA, Article 16, commentary (7).

⁶¹ GPSRIL, Principle 7, commentary (10).

⁶² GPSRIL, Principle 7, commentary (4).

⁶³ GPSRIL, Principle 7, commentary (8).

Thus, the operation of an arrangement whereby asylum seekers are subjected to detrimental conditions in Türkiye and Greece and are refused direct access to their national reception and asylum systems, is an attempt by EU Member States to evade legal responsibility.

4.2. CASE 2: Systemic responsibility with respect to the containment of refugee movements originating from Syria

4.2.1. Wrongful act

The wrongful acts identified in this case of systemic responsibility attribution consist of the violation of the right to leave any country, including one's own, and the right to seek asylum as a consequence of the containment of refugee movements in Türkiye following the implementation of the EU-Türkiye Statement.

4.2.2. Causation

From the perspective of containment, the EU-Türkiye Statement resulted in the following developments at the borders and in the territories of Türkiye and Greece⁶⁴:

- Türkiye prevented new arrivals from arriving to the EU and took measures to prevent the opening of any new sea or land routes for illegal migration from Türkiye to the EU;
- Greece designated Türkiye as a safe country and, as a consequence, regular classification of asylum claims by those who have arrived by sea were deemed inadmissible;
- Refugees from Greece whose asylum claims were rejected or found inadmissible were readmitted;
- Reported pushbacks by Greece together with Frontex operations at the Aegean Sea actively restricting mobility;
- Prolonged detention and confinement of refugees who have arrived in the Greek Islands by sea in hotspots, in detrimental conditions which deters mobility towards Greece;
- Funding of projects by the EU to support border management and the return capacity of Türkiye.

The first five developments serve to contain potential and actual refugees in Türkiye, while the last development serve to confine potential and actual refugees in Syria.

In the aftermath of the EU-Türkiye Statement, Türkiye closed its border with Syria and introduced visa requirements for Syrians. This denied Syrians in need of international protection the possibility to avail themselves of the right to seek asylum and to be protected against persecution and inhuman treatment in Syria⁶⁵. Türkiye also took active measures to

⁶⁴ TÜRKİYE Report 50.

⁶⁵ TÜRKİYE Report 4.

prevent irregular passages to Greece. Thus, the adoption of the EU-Türkiye Statement resulted in confining displaced persons to Syria as well as to Türkiye, which was an infringement of the right to leave any country including its own and the right to seek asylum⁶⁶.

4.2.3. Responsibility attribution

The intention of containment that underlies the EU-Türkiye Statement opens the door to arguments on systemic responsibility attribution to the EU and its Member States.

The right to asylum is guaranteed in Article 18 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. The EU-Türkiye Statement makes it more difficult for individuals from Syria in need of international protection to make use of their right to seek asylum due to their confinement in Türkiye and Syria⁶⁷. Whereas Article 18 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights provides for the right to asylum with reference to the Refugee Convention, the attempts to establish formal legal responsibility of the EU for its violation has so far failed due to considerations *ratione personae*⁶⁸. Moreover, the fact that the Charter does not bind Türkiye as a matter of law denies formal responsibility attribution to Türkiye, as the acts of containment of refugees in Türkiye and Syria do not qualify as wrongful under Article 12 ARSIWA on the existence of a breach of an international obligation and Article 13 ARSIWA on the international obligation being in force for a state. By consequence, a derivative formal legal responsibility of EU Member States under Article 16 ARSIWA on aid and assistance is not arguable.

The right to leave any country including one's own is laid down in Article 13(2) of the UDHR (as such not binding as a matter of international law) and Article 2(2) of Protocol No. 4 to the ECHR (ratified by neither Türkiye nor Greece). This right also finds a legal basis in Article 12(2) ICCPR which is binding for both Türkiye and Greece as well as for EU Member States.

The question arises whether the right to leave any country is infringed by measures of containment. One could anticipate an argument against there being a breach once alternative destinations are available for exercising the right. For example, it could be claimed that the harm sustained by the individuals contained in Türkiye, Serbia and Niger cannot be regarded as an infringement of their right to leave since the possibility of leaving for any other country, including their countries of origin, might still be open. This would apply even though the route to leave these countries bound for EU countries might be blocked (unless a person qualifies for resettlement in the case of Türkiye and Niger).

⁶⁶ TÜRKİYE Report 44-45.

⁶⁷ TÜRKİYE Report 44.

⁶⁸ In General Court of the European Union 28 February 2017, T192/16, NF v. European Council; General Court of the European Union 28 February 2017, T193/16, NG v. European Council; General Court of the European Union 28 February 2017, T257/16, NM v. European Council; it was denied that the EU-Türkiye Statement is entered into by the EU holding it legally not responsible.

Subscribing to Stoyanova's convincing analysis⁶⁹, we reject this proposition primarily because the possibility of leaving for other countries (for example, Niger's neighbours) cannot per se rule out an infringement of the right to leave. As held by the Human Rights Committee, the triggering of the application of Article 12(2) of the ICCPR need not entail a complete inability to leave the territory of a particular state. The Committee has found the provision applicable to circumstances where individuals could leave for one particular country but could not go to a country where they specifically wished to go⁷⁰.

One could also anticipate an argument against the applicability of the right to leave in cases of contained mobility, based on the claim that countries of destination are precisely seeking to facilitate such movement in an orderly fashion through their cooperation with host third countries (such as Türkiye, Serbia and Niger). However, that objective does not consume the right to leave. This conclusion is strengthened further, once we consider the level of protection in these host countries or the expected level of protection that migrants can avail themselves of in any alternative destination.

On this basis, we would like to emphasise that the right to leave any country including one's own might engender arguments attributing legal responsibility to actors jointly embarking on containment-related conduct. However, due to evidentiary and justiciability concerns, as well as the sizeable endeavour of capturing the overall policy purposes underlying the EU-Türkiye Statement, this case is considered to be a likely candidate for an argument on systemic responsibility attribution.

As expressed by the respondents in the field study on Türkiye, '*although the EU-Türkiye Statement on paper does not violate international law, its implementation (and especially its containment focus) raises issues with regard to the compatibility of these arrangements with fundamental rights including the right to seek asylum*⁷¹.' In general terms, containment aims at preventing movement of irregular migrants and asylum seekers towards the EU. Part of its rationale is to evade legal responsibility of the EU or its Member States by preventing the establishment of a jurisdictional link between a relevant third country national and European actors⁷². The limitation of the freedom of movement, the right to leave any country including one's own and the right to seek asylum is the underlying purpose of the EU-Türkiye Statement. Moreover, despite considerable support by the EU to improving conditions in Türkiye through the funds mobilised in connection with the EU-Türkiye Statement, the implementation of the Statement has increased the pressure on protection systems in Türkiye and Greece and thus conflicts with the GCR objective of easing the pressures on host countries⁷³.

⁶⁹ Stoyanova, V. (2020), 'The Right to Leave Any Country and the Interplay between Jurisdiction and Proportionality in Human Rights Law', *International Journal of Refugee Law* 403–439.

⁷⁰ HRC, *Loubna El Ghar v Libya*, UN doc CCPR/C/82/D/1107/2002 (15 November 2004).

⁷¹ TÜRKİYE Report 4.

⁷² TÜRKİYE Report 10.

⁷³ TÜRKİYE Report 55.

4.3. CASE 3: Systemic responsibility with respect to coproduction of refugee movements originating from Syria

4.3.1. Wrongful act

Similar to Case 1 above, the wrongful acts identified in this case of systemic responsibility consist of human rights violations arising from substandard protection and reception of migrants and refugees in Türkiye that take place in the course of refugee movements originating from Syria since 2011.

4.3.2. Causation

The reasons why protection and reception conditions in Türkiye are to be classified as substandard were explained above under Case 1. Here, the analysis will focus on how actions of the EU and selected Member States, specifically France and the Netherlands, subjected migrants and refugees to these conditions. We emphasise that our mission in this report is to identify arguable attribution arguments – which does not necessarily mean that these arguments are endorsed from an ethical point of view. The fact that a significant number of EU Member States were involved in the regional dynamics surrounding the Syrian Civil War, and the subsequent mass influx originating from Syria is widely known⁷⁴. Specific instances of such involvement by France and the Netherlands are mentioned below as examples to establish the link of causation. This constitutes a model for a systemic responsibility attribution argument, capturing the impact of engagement and cooperation in different policy areas and the historical dimension of the asylum realm. That said, we find it arguable that the political and military involvement of the EU and of EU Member States in the Syrian conflict, and the process leading to it, contributed in complex ways to the flow of asylum seekers from Türkiye to Syria, who ended up facing being exposed to substandard protection and reception conditions in Türkiye. This flow also caused a further deterioration of substandard conditions due to increasing pressure on reception resources through mass influx⁷⁰. Our arguments are aimed at establishing a causal link between the element of engagement and legal responsibility, and not to quantify the outcomes of such engagement.

Extending from its colonial mandate status in Syria in the aftermath of World War I to supply weaponry and equipment to Syria, France has deep-rooted historical relations and interests in the region⁷⁵. Although with changing positionality, at times France supported

⁷⁴ Yırcalı, Ü. (2017), 'Europe and the Syrian Conflict: Policies and Perceptions', Public Policy and Democracy Studies Publications, p.8-16; Bouris, A. and A. Nacrou, (2017), 'The Ins and Outs of the EU's Shortcomings in Syria, European Institute of the Mediterranean, p.90-95.

⁷⁵ Shorrock, W.I. (2009), 'The Origin of the French Mandate in Syria and Lebanon: The Railroad Question, 1901–1914', 1, *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, 133; Spagnolo, J. P. (1969) 'French Influence in Syria Prior to World War I: The Functional Weakness of Imperialism', 23 *Middle East Journal* 45; Jackson, S. (2014), 'Global Recruitment: The Wartime Origins of French Mandate Syria', in L. Broch and A. Carrol (eds), *France in an Era of Global War, 1914–1945: Occupation, Politics, Empire and Entanglements*, Palgrave Macmillan UK; Fieldhouse, D.K (2008), 'Syria and the French, 1918–1946', *Western Imperialism in the Middle*

the Arab Spring⁷⁶ which by extension led to the Syrian Civil War⁷⁷. In the course of the Syrian Civil War, France sustained active political and diplomatic engagement ranging from demanding that Assad step down and proposing a UN resolution for protection of civilians harmed by the forces of the Syrian government to calling for military intervention⁷⁸. As of 2012 France also provided support to the opposition forces through different means which include arms and non-lethal military aid including means of communication and protection⁷⁹.

East 1914-1958, Oxford University Press; Dufourcq, J. and O. Kempf (2016), 'The Evolution of France's Policy in Syria', p.8–13; 'The French in Syria – a Long and Tortured History' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20220424181519/https://limacharlieneews.com/foreign-policy/french-in-syria>>.

- ⁷⁶ 'Sarkozy: Critical That G8 Support Arab "Spring"' <<https://www.voanews.com/a/sarkozy-critical-that-g8-support-arab-spring-122687034/139951.html>>; 'Closing Speech by Mr. Alain Juppé French Minister of Foreign and European Affairs at the Arab Spring Symposium' (Brookings Institution Washington, 6 June 2011); Börzel, T., T. Risse, and A. Dandashly (2015), 'The EU, External Actors, and the Arabellions: Much Ado About (Almost) Nothing', *Journal of European Integration*, Vol. 37, 143; Lakomy, M. (2012), 'The "Arab Spring" in French Foreign Policy', *Central European Journal of International and Security Studies*, Vol. 6, p.71-74; Barah, M. (2012), 'France and the Arab Spring: An Opportunistic Quest for Influence', *Fundación para las Relaciones Internacionales y el Diálogo Exterior* (FRIDE), Working Paper, 8-10; Krüger, L.T. and B. Stahl (2018), 'The French Foreign Policy U-Turn in the Arab Spring – The Case of Tunisia', *Mediterranean Politics*, Vol. 23, p.207-209; Aras, I. (2017), 'Fransa'nın Arap Baharı Politikası', *Türkiye Ortadoğu Çalışmaları Dergisi*, Vol 4, pp.144-147.
- ⁷⁷ Joya, A. (2012), 'Syria and the Arab Spring: The Role of the Domestic and External Factors', *Ortadoğu Etütleri*, Vol 4, p.31-35; Lynch, M., D. Freelon and S. Aday (2014), 'Syria in the Arab Spring: The Integration of Syria's Conflict with the Arab Uprisings, 2011–2013' 1 *Research & Politics*, Vol. 6; Çakmak, C. and M. Ustaoglu (2015), 'The Arab Spring and the Emergence of the Syrian Crisis', *Post-Conflict Syrian State and Nation Building: Economic and Political Development*, Palgrave Macmillan U, p.20-22.
- ⁷⁸ Black, I. (2015), 'France More Active than Rest of the West in Tackling Syria', *The Guardian*, (www.theguardian.com/world/2015/nov/14/france-active-policy-syria-assad-isis-paris-attacks-air-strikes); *The Guardian* (2013), 'France Could Act on Syria without Britain, Says François Hollande' *Theguardian.Com*, ([web.archive.org/web/20130910204137/http://www.theguardian.com/world/2013/aug/30/france-act-on-syria-without-britain-hollande](http://www.theguardian.com/world/2013/aug/30/france-act-on-syria-without-britain-hollande)).
- ⁷⁹ Myard, J. (2015), 'The Real Stakes' *World Policy Journal*, Vol. 32, 77, 81; 'France Gives Non-Lethal Military Aid to Syrian Opposition: PM' <<https://english.alarabiya.net/articles/2012/08/22/233570>>.

By 2013 this had escalated to an announcement of its readiness to supply weapons⁸⁰, which was confirmed by France in 2014⁸¹. This was followed by French airstrikes in Syria in 2015 targeting ISIS⁸².

Whereas not as complex as the French involvement, the Netherlands also defended that Assad should step down and openly supported the opposition groups in the Syrian Civil War⁸³. Moreover, the Netherlands admitted its funding to Syrian opposition groups between 2015 and 2018⁸⁴. By 2016 the Dutch joined the US-led coalition against ISIS and military operations to Syria⁸⁵.

Beyond individual Member States, EU conduct with respect to the Syrian Civil War might also be considered as a potential trigger of systemic responsibility. The EU did not take a

⁸⁰ FRANCE 24 (2013), 'France's Hollande Hints at Arming Syrian Rebels', FRANCE 24, (www.france24.com/en/20130920-france-says-ready-arm-syrian-rebels-hollande-assad-fsa-islamists).

⁸¹ News Wires (2014), 'France Delivered Arms to Syrian Rebels, Hollande Confirms', FRANCE 24, (www.france24.com/en/20140821-france-arms-syria-rebels-hollande).

⁸² 'France Launches Air Strikes against Islamic State in Syria | Reuters' <<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-mideast-crisis-france-syria-idUSKCNORR07Y20150927/#eReZqrtoolY13th4.97>>; Sky News (2015), 'French Airstrikes in Syria "Self Defence"', Sky News, (web.archive.org/web/20151122110244/http://www.skynews.com.au/news/top-stories/2015/11/16/france-bombs-i-s--stronghold-in-syria.html); 'France Strikes ISIS Targets in Syria in Retaliation for Attacks - The New York Times' <https://web.archive.org/web/20151120075900/http://www.nytimes.com/2015/11/16/world/europe/paris-terror-attack.html?_r=0>; 'Raqqa Strikes: French Jets Bomb ISIS' Syria Stronghold - CNN.Com' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20151119221911/http://edition.cnn.com/2015/11/16/middle-east/france-raqqa-airstrikes-on-isis/>>; 'France Hits Back at Russia over Syria Bombing Campaign | Reuters' <<https://web.archive.org/web/2015112222501/http://uk.reuters.com/article/2015/11/20/u-k-mideast-crisis-france-russia-idUKKCN0T929420151120>>.

⁸³ Nieuwsbericht (2012), 'Rosenthal Spreekt Oppositie Syrië', Rijksoverheid.NL, (web.archive.org/web/20160405125150/https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/actueel/nieuws/2012/03/08/rosenthal-spreekt-oppositie-syrie).

⁸⁴ Dutch News (2018), 'Dutch Funded "jihadist" Group in Syria, Terror Trial May Now Falter', Dutch News, (www.dutchnews.nl/news/2018/09/dutch-funded-jihadist-group-in-syria-terror-trial-may-now-falter/); 'Syria: Dutch Gov't Prosecuted Levantine Front Member, Then Admitted They Supported It' <<https://www.juancole.com/2018/09/prosecuted-levantine-supported.html>>.

⁸⁵ Al Arabiya News (2020), 'Dutch to Join US-Led Airstrikes against ISIS in Syria', Al Arabiya English, (english.alarabiya.net/News/middle-east/2016/01/30/Dutch-to-join-US-led-airstrikes-against-ISIS-in-Syria); 'Support for Deployment of F-16s against IS in Eastern Syria | House of Representatives of the States General' <https://www.tweedekamer.nl/kamerstukken/plenaire_verslagen/kamer_in_het_kort/steun-voor-inzet-f-16s-tegen-oost-syrie>; 'The Netherlands Will Also Bomb IS in Syria' <<https://nos.nl/artikel/2083634-nederland-gaat-is-ook-in-syrie-bombarderen>>.

direct role in the military operations. However, starting in 2011, it imposed economic sanctions on Syria including an oil import ban and the freezing of assets in the EU, which worsened the conditions for ordinary people in Syria through their socio-economic impact. This entailed high inflation, an increase of poverty and of prices of goods and services as well as a breakdown of the civil economy and the acceleration of a war economy; these factors combined all contributed to the push factors for asylum flows⁸⁶.

4.3.3. Responsibility attribution

With all due caveats, we find systemic responsibility attribution to the European actors involved in the Syrian Civil War to be arguable. As identified above, the source of responsibility of the EU and its selected Member States (France and the Netherlands) is their contribution to coproduction of refugee movements originating from Syria through their political and military involvement in the Syrian Civil War and its precursor in the Arab Spring surrounded by their lasting historical connections with the region.

It would prove difficult to establish formal responsibility attribution under ARSIWA, ARIO and GPSRIL due to evidentiary issues for linking the political and military involvement in the Syrian Civil War with the human rights violations that the refugee population faces in Türkiye. The model of formal responsibility attribution is designed to hold the imminent wrongdoers responsible and falls short of capturing the hypercomplexity that is the reality triggering refugee movements⁸⁷.

Nevertheless, there is no doubt about the role of the European actors in the displacement from Syria which is the direct cause of this population being exposed to the substandard reception and protection. At this point, arguments on systemic responsibility come into play, and complex and multi-layered relationships need to be unpacked in an effort to hold the contributing actors legally responsible.

The wrongful acts of human rights violations within the asylum system in Türkiye were primarily authored by the Turkish state. However, limiting the analysis to this fundamental chain of responsibility overlooks more extensive circles of responsibility involvement. The political and military involvement of European actors in Syria are not the direct and immediate causes of human rights violations in Türkiye. However, this involvement formed part of a course of events that exposed the refugees to these conditions. Alternative measures such as a responsibility-sharing mechanism in the EU or

⁸⁶ Turkmani, R. and H. Mustafa (2016), 'The Role of the EU in the Syrian Conflict', SiT/WP/05/16 14–18; Tejero, M. (2022), 'The Role of the EU in the Syrian Conflict and the Hunt for a New Strategy', Universidad de Navarra, (<https://www.unav.edu/web/global-affairs/the-role-of-the-eu-in-the-syrian-conflict-and-the-hunt-for-a-new-strategy>); Veen, E. and et al. (2021), 'Band-Aids Not Bullets: EU Policies and Interventions in the Syrian and Iraqi Civil Wars', Clingendael Netherlands Institute of International Relations (CRU), reports, 23–24.

⁸⁷ Chimni, B.S. (2021), 'The Articles on State Responsibility and the Guiding Principles of Shared Responsibility: A TWAIL Perspective', *European Journal of International Law*, Vol. 31 No. 4, 1–11, p. 1216; Naef, B. (2019), 'The Responsibility of Home States for Violations of International Obligations by Their Corporate Citizens in Fragile States', Doctoral Dissertation, University of British Columbia, p.258–260.

enlarged resettlement quotas that provide direct access to asylum on EU territories could have been, but were not developed. Parallel to the logic behind the prohibition of chain *refoulement* and the requirement of opposability in international legal responsibility whereby “*a State cannot do by another what it cannot do by itself*”⁸⁸, systemic responsibility attribution is an effort to unveil evasion of legal responsibility by adapting it to the dynamics surrounding asylum flows.

⁸⁸ ARSIWA, article 16, commentary (6).

5. Tunisia

5.1. CASE 1: Formal responsibility with respect to substandard asylum procedures and reception conditions in Tunisia

5.1.1. Wrongful act

The wrongful acts identified in this case of formal responsibility attribution consist of human rights violations, especially violations of the right to an effective remedy, arising from the deficiencies in the refugee status determination (RSD) procedures and from conditions of reception of migrants and refugees in Tunisia as carried out by UNHCR. Accordingly, UNHCR's responsibility is triggered as the actor carrying out RSD procedures and reception, and Tunisia's responsibility is triggered as the legal obligation for carrying out RSD procedures and reception belongs to the state of Tunisia which it delegated to UNHCR.

5.1.2. Causation

This case of formal responsibility attribution rests on two dimensions. The first one is the due process violations observed within RSD procedures and the second one is the substandard conditions in the system of reception of migrants and refugees, which are outsourced by the Tunisian State to UNHCR⁸⁹.

Due process violations within RSD procedures

Against the background of lack of a domestic legislative framework regulating the asylum system, there is no central governmental authority in Tunisia undertaking asylum governance. The RSD process has been carried out by UNHCR since 2011 on the basis of its mandate as recognised in its Cooperation Agreement with Tunisia⁹⁰. UNHCR's RSD process suffers from financial and administrative limitations affecting rights and services available to asylum seekers and refugees. These limitations include insufficient capacity to respond to asylum applications, applicants not being given appropriate identification documents thus leading to problems in accessing services, lack of legal aid and prolonged

⁸⁹ Dimitriadi, A. (2022), "Migration and Asylum in Tunisia: Domestic interests, external influences, and policy outcomes", ASILE Report, (hereinafter Migration and Asylum in Tunisia Paper), No. 18, (https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/Migration-and-asylum-in-Tunisia_ASILE.pdf).

⁹⁰ UNHCR (2016), 'Submission by the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees for the Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights', Compilation Report, Universal Periodic Review: 3rd Cycle, 27th Session, Tunisia, (<https://uprdoc.ohchr.org/uprweb/downloadfile.aspx?filename=3967&file=EnglishTranslation>).

processing time for applications. Despite such problems, UNHCR submits that RSD procedures are aligned with the framework of the Refugee Convention⁹¹.

Another problem is the lack of judicial review of RSD decisions. Once issued, negative decisions within UNHCR RSD procedures are final, and except for internal complaint mechanisms, there are no legal remedies available, whether based on procedural rights associated with the RSD process or based on substantial aspects related to risk of persecution. Low approval rates for asylum applications in Tunisia make the lack of the right to appeal ever more pressing as an issue⁹².

While applicants have access to the internal complaint mechanisms of the UNHCR, these are not compliant with international standards. The internal complaint mechanism of UNHCR is not specifically designed for appealing negative asylum decisions, but covers the general scope of activities of UNHCR and its implementing partner non-governmental organisations. Such complaint procedures comprise of complaint boxes at physical premises or email addresses where complaints can be lodged on an anonymous basis. Another avenue is UNHCR's Inspector-General Office⁹³ headquarters in Geneva which can be contacted by complainants directly or by UNHCR country offices. The Inspector-General's Office conducts independent confidential investigations. In any case these procedures target general human rights violations that may occur within the general scope of activities of UNHCR and its implementing partner non-governmental organisations rather than review UNCHR RSD asylum decisions⁹⁴.

Due process standards, such as the possibility to appeal negative RSD decisions, are crucial components of the RSD process as reflected in well-established UNHCR instruments. UNHCR Executive Committee Conclusion No. 8 on Determination of Refugee Status provides that in case of non-recognition of an asylum applicant, reasonable time should be given for appeal with the purpose of a formal reconsideration of the decision⁹⁵. Moreover, RSD is defined as a core UNHCR protection function pursuant to UNHCR's mandate, and the right to appeal an RSD decision by applicants whose RSD decision was negative at first instance is among the core standards for due process in the RSD

⁹¹ Raach, F. and H. Sha'ath and T. Spijkerboer, Country Report TUNISIA WP5. Country Reports, (hereinafter TUNISIA Report), No. 55, 65-66(https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/D5.2_WP5-Tunisia-Country-Report-Final.pdf); Migration and Asylum in Tunisia Paper 18, 25.

⁹² TUNISIA Report 4-5, 52; Migration and Asylum in Tunisia Paper 24; Giuffr, M., C. Denaro and F. Raach, (2022) 'On "Safety" and EU Externalization of Borders: Questioning the Role of Tunisia as a "Safe Country of Origin" and a "Safe Third Country"', *European Journal of Migration and Law*, Vol. 24, Issue 4, p. 597.

⁹⁴ TUNISIA Report 4-5, 50-51.

⁹⁵ UNHCR, Executive Committee, Determination of Refugee Status No. 8 (XXVIII) - 1977, para. (vi), [12 October 1977](https://www.refworld.org/docid/3ae68c6e4.html), (<https://www.refworld.org/docid/3ae68c6e4.html>).

mandate⁹⁶. In defining the scope of the right to appeal, it is maintained that every asylum applicant whose RSD decision was negative at first instance has the right to appeal that negative RSD decision providing a review of both findings of fact and the application of the refugee criteria under UNHCR's mandate. It is also of paramount importance that the applicants continue to enjoy the rights and protection accorded to them as registered asylum seekers or refugees throughout the appeal period⁹⁷. As confirmed elsewhere, UNHCR considers that the right to appeal negative RSD decisions is part of the right to an effective remedy in asylum cases, within accelerated procedures as well⁹⁸.

Finally, it is accepted that the right to appeal negative RSD decisions is also provided within the framework of the ICCPR in consideration of the *non-refoulement* principle and the general obligation of providing an effective remedy concerning violations of rights protected under ICCPR⁹⁹. Such a right to appeal is required to be available both in practice as well as in law; it should be accessible and should provide a binding decision with the possibility of appropriate relief¹⁰⁰. Similar formulation also exists in Article 7(1)(a) ACHPR which is binding for Tunisia.

Reception conditions

Similar to RSD procedures, the reception of migrants and asylum seekers in Tunisia is also outsourced to UNHCR. As the situation stands there are challenges for applicants in terms of access to residence permits and the labour market, as well as the limited term of stay in reception centres¹⁰¹. Reception centres are operated by the Tunisian Red Crescent, IOM, and UNHCR which provide temporary and short-term accommodation with limited capacity¹⁰².

⁹⁶ UNHCR, Procedural Standards for Refugee Status Determination Under UNHCR's Mandate, 14-15, 26 August 2020, (<https://www.refworld.org/docid/5e870b254.html>).

⁹⁷ UNHCR, Procedural Standards for Refugee Status Determination Under UNHCR's Mandate, 26 August 2020, p. 270.

⁹⁸ UNHCR Executive Committee, The Problem of Manifestly Unfounded or Abusive Applications for Refugee Status or Asylum No. 30 (XXXIV) - 1983, para. (e) (iii), 20 October 1983, (<https://www.refworld.org/publisher,EXCOM,EXCONC,,3ae68c6118,0.html>); UNHCR Statement on the Right to an Effective Remedy in relation to Accelerated Asylum Procedures, para. 21, 21 May 2010, (<https://www.unhcr.org/media/unhcr-statement-right-effective-remedy-relation-accelerated-asylum-procedures>).

⁹⁹ UN Human Rights Committee, General Comment No. 31, Adopted on 29 March 2004, 2187th meeting, para. 12.

¹⁰⁰ Wouters, K. (2009), 'International Legal Standards for the Protection from Refoulement, A Legal Analysis of the Prohibitions on Refoulement Contained in the Refugee Convention, the European Convention on Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the Convention against Torture', *Intersentia*, p. 628; Boeles, P. (1997), 'Fair Immigration Proceedings in Europe', *Martinus Nijhoff Publishers*, p. 109.

¹⁰¹ Migration and Asylum in Tunisia Paper 18.

¹⁰² TUNISIA Report 56.

Financial limitations lead to insufficient assistance and accommodation, UNHCR sources are not able to provide asylum seekers with the adequate living standards they need¹⁰³. There were widespread protests by migrants about sub-standard reception conditions in 2022¹⁰⁴.

The Refugee Convention provides for incremental standards of reception to be available to asylum seekers depending on the nature of their presence on host state territory. At minimum, this covers matters related to non-discrimination, religion, exemption from reciprocity, personal status, access to courts, rationing and public education. On account of the gradual structure of the Refugee Convention, where certain rights enshrined therein are conditional on recognition as a refugee, many of them are triggered merely by presence within the territory. Moreover, the rights enshrined in international human rights instruments that are applicable in Tunisia including the UDHR, ICCPR and the ICESCR cover everyone including asylum seekers. Article 11(1) ICESCR provides for the right of all individuals to an adequate standard of living, which includes the provision of food, clothing and accommodation. Articles 7, 9, 10 and 14 ICCPR provide protection against arbitrary detention and torture, and the right to recognition everywhere as a person before the law. They also envisage that these rights are applicable to everyone without any distinction of any kind which builds a clear basis for their application to asylum seekers. Moreover, the CEDAW, CRC and the African Charter also provide rights that are relevant for the standard of treatment in reception of asylum seekers. In line with this international legal framework and in an effort to formulate common standards for reception measures for asylum seekers, UNHCR identifies recommendations covering documentation and temporary residence status; assistance, including accommodation, means of subsistence and employment; health care; education; freedom of movement and detention; family unity; groups with special needs, including children, women, and the elderly¹⁰⁵. UNHCR also has other efforts for setting forth measures and standards relevant to reception of asylum seekers¹⁰⁶.

5.1.3. Responsibility attribution

Whereas the actual conduct by UNHCR and consent to such conduct by the Tunisian government relevant to the wrongful acts outlined above concerning RSD procedures and reception conditions is clear, we see two avenues to structure an argument of formal legal responsibility allocation to relevant actors under ARSIWA, ARIO and GPSRIL. Considering the intertwined nature and wide scope of legal and policy cooperation based on the Cooperation Agreement of 2011 between the UNHCR and Tunisia, the distinction between the principal actor and the ancillary actor is blurred, which allows construction of the legal responsibility case in both ways. In any case it is possible to argue for Tunisia's evasion of legal responsibility

¹⁰³ TUNISIA Report 71; Migration and Asylum in Tunisia Paper 24.

¹⁰⁴ Migration and Asylum in Tunisia Paper 25.

¹⁰⁵ UNHCR, Reception of Asylum-Seekers, Including Standards of Treatment, in the Context of Individual Asylum Systems, EC/GC/01/17, 2001, 7-10.

¹⁰⁶ UNHCR, Policy on Refugee Protection and Solutions in Urban Areas, September 2009, (<https://www.refworld.org/docid/4ab8e7f72.html>); UNHCR, Policy on Alternatives to Camps, UNHCR/HCP/2014/9, 22 July 2014, (<https://www.refworld.org/docid/5423ded84.html>).

by outsourcing the RSD and reception functions to UNHCR which would normally be incumbent upon the state as the provider of international protection within its territory in the place of national protection that asylum seekers are lacking.

Attribution of responsibility to the UNHCR as the principal actor

Taking the actions of UNHCR (i.e. the taking of negative RSD decisions without the possibility of appeal and of providing substandard reception conditions for asylum seekers) as a basis for responsibility attribution makes UNHCR the principal actor. Tunisia then would have a derivative role in referring asylum seekers to the operations of UNHCR which is the setting for the wrongful acts.

UNHCR's formal legal responsibility can be established on the basis of Article 3 ARIO which provides that internationally wrongful acts of international organisations entail the international responsibility of that organisation and Article 4 ARIO which identifies the elements of an international wrongful act of an international organisation as an act or omission attributable to the organisation and that constitutes a breach of an international obligation. Wrongful acts arising from RSD and reception procedures conducted by UNHCR clearly satisfy these conditions. It should be noted that the commentary of Article 5 ARIO clarifies that international law governs the characterisation of an act of an international organisation as internationally wrongful and the rules of the international organisations should be viewed as part of international law¹⁰⁷ which covers in this case the UNHCR standards on RSD and reception conditions explained above. Accordingly, as per Article 6 ARIO, actions of agents of UNHCR in Tunisia constitute acts attributable to UNHCR.

In connection with the principal acts of UNHCR, it is observed that the Tunisian State is complicit in the wrongful acts of UNHCR through referral of asylum seekers to the operations of UNHCR and such complicity constitutes an autonomous wrongful act in itself. In this respect it is possible to base Tunisia's legal responsibility on Article 58 ARIO on aid or assistance by a state in the commission of an internationally wrongful act by an international organisation. In view of the explanations in the commentary, the fact that in line with their Cooperation Agreement, Tunisia extends support to the activities of UNHCR concerning RSD and reception procedures in its territory, which would be breaching the same international norms if they were conducted by Tunisia, should be considered to qualify as aid and assistance within the meaning of this article¹⁰⁸.

Attribution of responsibility to Tunisia as the principal actor

By considering Tunisia's delegation of RSD and reception functions to UNHCR as the basis for responsibility attribution, Tunisia becomes the principal actor. UNHCR then has a secondary role in carrying out its operations that involve wrongful acts, and this is based on Tunisia's general consent.

Following a reverse symmetry of the above reasoning on attribution of responsibility, Tunisia's responsibility arises from Articles 12 and 13 ARSIWA which provide that a state

¹⁰⁷ ARIO, Article 5, Commentary (2).

¹⁰⁸ ARIO, Article 58, Commentary (2-3).

is responsible for a breach of international obligations in force for that state that are applicable to Tunisia's assent to UNHCR operations on its territory involving RSD procedures without right to appeal and substandard reception conditions. Per Article 4 ARSIWA, actions carried out by its organs constitute acts attributable to Tunisia.

Owing to its lack of capacity and infrastructure, Tunisia has agreed to the presence of UNHCR and has entirely outsourced operation of RSD and reception on Tunisian territory to UNHCR. UNCHR's responsibility in return is triggered by its conduct within RSD and by reception procedures which constitute aid and assistance to the principal wrongful act of Tunisia under Article 14 ARIO.

This full legal analysis underlines once more that the choice of engaging either Articles 3, 4 and 5 ARIO in combination with Article 58 ARIO or Articles 12 and 13 ARSIWA together with 14 ARIO is possible. Presenting both formulations here demonstrates different tools available in international law of responsibility to capture the human rights violations that occur within the modalities of cooperation between a state and UNHCR and that they are sufficient to lift the veil of hypercomplexity and preclude evasion of responsibility.

5.2. CASE 2: Systemic responsibility with respect to the containment of refugee movements in Tunisia

5.2.1. Wrongful act

The wrongful acts identified in this case of systemic responsibility attribution consist of the violation of the right to leave any country including one's own and the right to seek asylum as a consequence of the containment of refugee movements in Tunisia through pullbacks that take place in the course of maritime cooperation and Integrated Border Management (IBM) as implemented by ICMPD.

5.2.2. Causation

An overview of areas of international cooperation in support of migration management by Tunisia reveals the involved actors' underlying motivation of containment of refugees in Tunisia. Accordingly, international cooperation with Tunisia as supported by the EU and its Member States centre around border management including maritime operations for search and rescue (SAR), and interceptions at sea as well as IBM as implemented by ICMPD.

The EU's three funding instruments available to Tunisia, namely the European Union Emergency Trust Fund for Stability and Combating the Root Causes of Irregular Migration and the Displaced Persons in Africa (EUTF); the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF); and the regional European Neighbourhood Instrument (ENI) which total EUR 58 million, EUR 55 million of which is used for border management, showcase the policy priorities of the EU in its cooperation with Tunisia. This is also reflected in the bilateral cooperation of EU Member States such as Italy and Germany in their bilateral cooperation with Tunisia that centre around financial and technical assistance to border management through procurement of patrol boats and surveillance equipment. IBM is implemented within the framework of the EU funding instrument EUTF with the objectives of combating irregular migration and mitigating vulnerabilities that arise from irregular migration

through establishment of an institutional framework for monitoring and controlling borders. IBM is implemented on the ground by ICMPD and it is ultimately a process with actions such as providing equipment for screening and surveillance, capacity building for border officials including border guards, police, and coastguard as well as establishing inter-institutional coordination at national level and supporting the development of Tunisia's National Strategy on Border Security. To this end ICMPD supports line ministries and other national actors involved in border management by providing training and technical expertise. As part of IBM, the Integrated System for Maritime Surveillance (ISMariS) has been developed; this is a monitoring tool for the Tunisian coast that will facilitate SAR operations and interceptions¹⁰⁹.

Overall, European states and ICMPD provide funding and technical assistance to Tunisia basically for the interception and return of boats departing from its shores. This modality comes across as an attempt to evade legal responsibility that would otherwise be triggered in case of interception / SAR operations directly carried out by EU agents as in the case of operations *Mare Nostrum* and *Sophia*. So instead of carrying out pushbacks, the EU, its Member States and ICMPD extend support to Tunisia that eventually enables pullbacks¹¹⁰.

5.2.3. Responsibility attribution

Whereas financial and technical cooperation by the EU, its Member States and ICMPD¹¹¹ may trigger international responsibility under ARSIWA and ARIO¹¹², these formal legal responsibility models require that such cooperation contributes significantly to the wrongful act and fall short of capturing the overall containment perspective in the migration cooperation of foreign actors with Tunisia. Moreover, evidentiary issues arise in identifying the degree of individual contributions to joint responsibility in view of the relations and cooperation between Tunisia and ICMPD as well as ICMPD and its member states. Finally, the right to leave and the right to seek asylum do not appear for all actors involved as formal international legal obligations, the breach of which would trigger formal responsibility¹¹³. Thus, we suggest the model of systemic responsibility to capture the indirect yet tangible sequence of actions that serve the purpose of containment of refugees in Tunisia.

¹⁰⁹ Migration and Asylum in Tunisia Paper 20-21.

¹¹⁰ TUNISIA Report 58-59.

¹¹¹ For the purpose of analysis here it should be clarified that ICMPD is an international organisation with 20 member states and the Agreement on the Establishment and Functioning of ICMPD entered into force in 1993, (<https://www.icmpd.org/about-us/about-icmpd>).

¹¹² Kienast, J., NF. Tan and J. Vedsted-Hansen (2023), 'Human Rights Compatibility & Attribution of Responsibility', p .50-53.

¹¹³ On this account for example Tunisian Law 2004-6 dated 3 February 2004 that is still in effect and officially aimed at fighting against human trafficking, prohibits the right to leave to seek protection abroad for migrants and for Tunisian nationals alike.

Considering the human rights violations within the asylum system as outlined in Case 1 above, the instances of collective expulsions of migrants and asylum seekers to Libya and the general informality in migration management due to the absence of relevant legislation, it is possible to conclude that the safety of refugees contained in through SAR operations and strengthened border management is uncertain¹¹⁴. However, beyond these issues of compatibility with international law that arise from the question of whether Tunisia can be considered as a safe place of disembarkation in interception / SAR operations, we argue that EU support for such maritime operations effectively serves the overall purpose of obstructing the departure of refugees from Tunisia to the detriment of the right to leave and the right to seek asylum.

5.3. CASE 3: Systemic responsibility with respect to coproduction of refugee movements originating from Libya

5.3.1. Wrongful act

Similar to Case 1 above, the wrongful acts identified in this case of systemic responsibility consist of human rights violations arising from shortcomings in the RSD procedures and the substandard reception conditions of migrants and refugees in Tunisia. These issues occur in the course of refugee movements originating from Libya.

5.3.2. Causation

Deficiencies in the RSD procedures and substandard reception conditions in Tunisia were explained above under Case 1. Here, the analysis will focus on how actions of the EU and selected EU Member States, specifically France and Italy, caused migrants and refugees to be subject to these conditions. We argue that the political and military involvement of the EU and of EU Member States in the Libyan Civil War contributed to the movement of asylum seekers from Libya who then ended up facing deficient RSD procedures and substandard reception conditions in Tunisia. This movement caused, in turn, a further deterioration of substandard conditions due to increasing pressure on both the asylum system and reception resources of the host state.

As soon as the civil war broke out in Libya in 2011, UNHCR declared the situation to be a 'humanitarian disaster' with an influx of refugees fleeing the country¹¹⁵. Border crossings to Tunisia included Libyan nationals as well as nationals of Egypt, Tunisia and Türkiye¹¹⁶.

¹¹⁴ Migration and Asylum in Tunisia Paper 24; TUNISIA Report 60.

¹¹⁵ Saunders, D. (2011), 'At a Tense Border Crossing, a Systematic Effort to Keep Black Africans out - The Globe and Mail', Web Article, ([web.archive.org/web/20170204081847/http://www.theglobeandmail.com/news/world/africa-mideast/at-a-tense-border-crossing-a-systematic-effort-to-keep-black-africans-out/article1925955/](http://www.theglobeandmail.com/news/world/africa-mideast/at-a-tense-border-crossing-a-systematic-effort-to-keep-black-africans-out/article1925955/)).

¹¹⁶ Saunders, D. (2011), 'Live Update: Thousands Flee across Libya-Tunisia Border - The Globe and Mail', Report from the scene, (<https://web.archive.org/web/20110301021532/http://www.theglobeandmail.com/news/wo>

Within three years of the start of the conflict, the number of refugees originating from Libya hosted in Tunisia reached around a million which is nearly 20 % of its own population. Including Libyan refugees spread to other countries this means that approximately one third of Libya's entire population has fled the country¹¹⁷. As a reflection of this, in addition to land passages by asylum seekers towards Egypt and Tunisia, the sea passages and thus interceptions by the Libyan coast guard have also dramatically increased¹¹⁸. Impacts of the Libyan Civil War on Tunisia are still considered to continue in terms of cross-border movement¹¹⁹. Building on this initial premise the causal link between the civil war in Libya and the increased refugee movements towards Tunisia is undisputed. What remains to be clarified is the contribution of the European actors to the conflicts and the simultaneous refugee movements to Tunisia.

European states became involved in the region following the start of the Libyan Civil War in March 2011. As NATO-led military operations to enforce the UN Security Council resolution declaring a no-fly zone ensued, France carried out air strikes targeting Libya¹²⁰. Other countries including Belgium, the Netherlands, Denmark, Spain, Italy, Greece and Norway also expressed prior support for a military invasion of Libya¹²¹. After the collapse of the regime in October 2011 there was widespread commitment in the international arena to support stability and democracy in Libya but in reality, military instability

<http://www.unhcr.org/refugees/2011/05/13/1918670/>); Wilkes, S. (2011), 'Hundreds of Libyan Berbers Flee Western Mountains and Head to Tunisia', UNHCR Website, (<https://www.unhcr.org/news/stories/hundreds-libyan-berbers-flee-western-mountains-and-head-tunisia>).

¹¹⁷ Mandraud I. (2014), Le Monde '«Kadhafi Est Toujours Là» Pour Les Libyens de Tunis' <https://www.lemonde.fr/international/article/2014/05/13/kadhafi-est-toujours-la-pour-les-libyens-de-tunis_4415916_3210.html>; Salvin, B. (2014), 'Tunisia's President Asks US for Help - Al-Monitor: Independent, Trusted Coverage of the Middle East', Al-Monitor Website, (<https://www.al-monitor.com/originals/2014/08/tunisia-africa-summit-terrorists-helicopters.html>); Anderson, J.L. (2015), 'Libya's New Strongman', The New Yorker, (www.newyorker.com/magazine/2015/02/23/unravelling).

¹¹⁸ The Week (2015), 'Libya's "devastating" Refugee Crisis: By the Numbers', (theweek.com/articles/484872/libyas-devastating-refugee-crisis-by-numbers); AP (2020), 'Major Rise in Migrants Stopped off Libya: UN Refugee Agency, World News, The Indian Express, (indianexpress.com/article/world/major-rise-in-migrants-stopped-off-libya-un-refugee-agency-6259994/).

¹¹⁹ Migration and Asylum in Tunisia Paper 19.

¹²⁰ BBC (2011), 'Libya: US, UK and France Attack Gaddafi Forces', BBC News, (www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-12796972>; 'France Uses Unexplosive Bombs in Libya: Spokesman'; English News (2011), 'France uses unexplosive bombs in Libya: spokesman', (web.archive.org/web/20110430052853/http://news.xinhuanet.com/english2010/world/2011-04/29/c_13850700.htm).

¹²¹ EU News, Business and Politics (2011), 'Qatar, Several EU States up for Libya Action: Diplomat', EU Business, (<https://www.eubusiness.com/news-eu/libya-unrest-summit.95v/>); Byron J. (2011) EJP, News | Germany 'Paris Summit Talks to Launch Military Action in Libya' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20110516041335/http://ejpress.org/article/news/germany/49710>>.

continued in the following years with the involvement of foreign powers. Throughout the conflicts, Italy and France, in particular, extended military support to opposing factions within Libya due to their diverging economic and security interests in the region¹²². France's rhetoric centred on anti-terrorism, while Italy supported a unified government that would reduce human mobility from Libya. In that sense, apart from humanitarian assistance, the EU's political, financial and operational involvement in the Libyan Civil War is deemed incoherent and mainly led by Member States and not its institutions¹²³.

5.3.3. Responsibility attribution

Involvement of European countries in the civil war in Libya calls for systemic responsibility attribution with respect to the human rights violations faced by asylum seekers in Tunisia who have been uprooted from Libya in the course of the civil war. Coproduction of refugee movements through political and military means establishes the origin of such responsibility.

Similar to the legal analysis concerning causation, legal argumentation with respect to responsibility attribution is parallel to the Case 2 Systemic Responsibility with respect to the Coproduction of Refugee Movements Originating from Syria under the Cases of Responsibility for Türkiye. Here too, ARSIWA, ARIO and GPSRIL may not allow formal responsibility attribution to be established due to evidentiary issues for linking the political and military involvement in the Libyan Civil War with the human rights violations that the refugee population faces in Tunisia because of lack of a direct chain of cause and effect. In reality, it is very clear that European actors were involved in the process surrounding the displacement of refugees from Libya which is the direct cause of exposure of this population to the substandard asylum procedures and reception conditions. The suggested model of systemic responsibility is an attempt to unfold the hyper-complex and multi-layered relationships and hold the contributing actors legally responsible.

For European actors, having a share in the responsibility for coproduction of refugee movements does not necessarily originate from a contribution to the increase in the number of refugees. Arguably, European interventions may have even decreased the number of refugees fleeing to Tunisia which may have been higher if Gaddafi was not stopped. However, the purpose here is not to measure the impact of the European engagement. The responsibility model suggested here rests on the idea that political and

¹²² ISPI (2022), 'The EU, NATO and the Libya Crisis: Scaling Ambitions Down', ISPI Website, (www.ispionline.it/en/publication/eu-nato-and-libya-crisis-scaling-ambitions-down-36663); Eljarh, M., 'Is Europe Exporting Instability to the Southern Mediterranean? Libya as a Case Study : IEMed', IEMed Website, (www.iemed.org/publication/is-europe-exporting-instability-to-the-southern-mediterranean-libya-as-a-case-study/); Kausch, K. (2020), 'Libya: How Europe Failed to End the War, Middle East Eye Website, (<https://www.middleeasteye.net/opinion/why-europe-has-lost-its-relevance-libya>).

¹²³ Llauger, LT. (2023), '(In)Coherent European Action in Libya? The EU's Approach to the Libyan Civil Wars', European student think tank, (<https://esthinktank.com/2023/05/03/incoherent-european-action-in-libya-the-eus-approach-to-the-libyan-civil-wars/>); 'The EU in Libya – CEPS' <<https://www.ceps.eu/the-eu-in-libya/>>.

military engagement with the conflict regions should trigger consequences in the form of legal responsibility. The purpose is to spot the engagement component, as legal responsibility is a logical extension of such engagement. European countries, being former colonial powers, based on their historical experience of acting in such conflict contexts, should be in a position to anticipate the outcomes and they become a part of the process leading to these outcomes through their interventions.

The wrongful acts of human rights violations within the asylum system in Tunisia were the doing of the Tunisian State and UNHCR as explained in Case 1 above. However, limiting the analysis to the immediate actors cannot capture the evasion of responsibility by the larger set of actors involved. The political and military involvement of European actors in Libya formed part of a course of complex events that resulted in exposure of refugees to certain human rights violations and the model of systemic responsibility establishes the link between such involvement and its consequences.

6. Serbia

Cases of responsibility for Serbia

6.1. CASE 1: Formal responsibility with respect to substandard protection and reception conditions in Serbia

6.1.1. Wrongful act

The wrongful acts identified in this case of formal responsibility attribution consist of human rights violations arising from substandard protection and reception of migrants and refugees in Serbia following the 2015 increased refugee movements in the region and the close cooperation with the EU to manage these movements.

6.1.2. Causation

In the context of the Serbia-EU visa liberalisation process, Serbia adopted its first Asylum law in 2007 and started building its asylum system in 2008, without having any previous experience or infrastructure. As part of the accession process¹²⁴, Serbia had to harmonise its domestic law with the EU *acquis* and to that end, Serbia adopted three main laws, i.e. Law on Foreigners (LOF)¹²⁵, Law on Asylum and Temporary Protection (LATP)¹²⁶, and Law on Border Control¹²⁷. EU agencies, including EASO were involved in both drafting the legislation and its implementation (training and support to officers)¹²⁸.

¹²⁴ See e.g., the Evaluation of Sector Approach under the Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance (IPA) cycle II, compared with the IPA II cycle (2007–2014), https://ec.europa.eu/neighbourhood-enlargement/system/files/2019-01/23914_rep_serbia.pdf.

¹²⁵ Law on Foreigners, Official Gazette RS 24/2018, 26 March 2018.

¹²⁶ Law on asylum and temporary protection, Official Gazette RS 24/2018, 26 March 2018.

¹²⁷ Law on Border Control Official Gazette RS 24/2018, 26 March 2018.

¹²⁸ Olga Djurovic, Rados Djurovic and Thomas Spijkerboer Country Report SERBIA WP5. Country Reports (hereinafter SERBIA Report) p. 47 https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/D5.2_WP5-Serbia-Country-Report-Final.pdf; <https://euaa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/IPA-II-activities-phase-I.pdf>

The Serbian reception and asylum system has been introduced and sustained through EU funding, especially given the role that Serbia played during the events of the Syrian refugee crisis¹²⁹. In fact, the EU has framed some of the funding projects benefiting Serbia as a means of implementing the GCR's principle of solidarity and responsibility sharing¹³⁰.

The 'Western Balkans Route Leaders Statement 2015', which was agreed on by leaders of the Western Balkans countries and by certain EU Member States (Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, North Macedonia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Romania, Serbia, and Slovenia), resulted in a 17-point Plan of Action, including the following goals: 'limiting secondary movements; supporting refugees and providing shelter and rest; managing the migration flows together; border management; tackling smuggling and trafficking'¹³¹.

A number of human rights violations have been reported on Serbian soil during that time, including dire living conditions, ill-treatment and *de facto* deprivation of liberty in various reception camps, violence against unaccompanied minors in the Bogovađa Asylum Centre, almost non-existent possibilities for obtaining international protection in Serbia, and existence of the 'Hungarian list'¹³², i.e. waiting list for entry to Hungary etc.

From a national point of view, Serbia has been perceived as a transit country and, therefore, authorities have been operating under the assumption that only urgent and humanitarian aid is needed for migrants in the country, to facilitate swift movement toward destination countries in the EU¹³³. As a result, most refugees and asylum seekers in Serbia have had an irregular status (*de facto* tolerated irregular stay) which has increased their vulnerability and risks to become victims of smuggling, trafficking, violence, discrimination or abuse¹³⁴.

The question of whether there is a general presumption of Serbia being a 'safe third country' for migrants and refugees has not settled before the courts. However, in the ECtHR judgment *Ilias and Ahmed*, the Court contented that the Hungarian authorities had not taken sufficient account of authoritative reports that asylum seekers returned to Serbia would run a real risk of summary removal to North Macedonia and Greece where they would be subjected to

¹²⁹

http://www.evropa.gov.rs/Documents/Home/DACU/12/193/SA_IPA_II_eval_Vol_1_final_on_19_March.pdf and https://ec.europa.eu/neighbourhood-enlargement/system/files/2019-01/23914_rep_serbia.pdf accessed 2 December 2022.

¹³⁰ See Global Refugee Forum Pledge Dashboard, 'EU Contribution to Burden and Responsibility Sharing' <https://globalcompactrefugees.org/pledges-contributions>.

¹³¹ European Union (2015), 'Leaders' Meeting on refugee flows along the Western Balkans Route: Leaders' Statement', 25 October, www.refworld.org/docid/563216cb4.html accessed 2 December 2022.

¹³² SERBIA Report p. 67; ECRE, AIDA Country Report Hungary, 2021 Update p. 24.

¹³³ SERBIA Report p. 86.

¹³⁴ SERBIA Report p. 36 and 67.

conditions incompatible with Article 3. The ECtHR therefore concluded that Hungary had failed to discharge its procedural obligations under Article 3¹³⁵.

The nature of EU cooperation with Serbia is similar to that of Türkiye, another EU candidate, as outlined in Case 1 on formal responsibility with respect to substandard protection and reception in Türkiye. The similarities are in terms of EU support for development of formerly non-existent asylum legislation in line with the EU acquis as well as political agreement to stop irregular movement towards the EU and human rights violations committed against such background which render its position as a safe third country questionable.

6.1.3. Responsibility attribution

Attribution of responsibility to Serbia

The operation of the asylum system in Serbia rests with its executive organs, and thus the wrongful acts committed on its territory – following the 2015 increased refugee movements in the region and the close cooperation with the EU to manage these movements, are attributable to Serbia under Article 4 ARSIWA. In particular, not having acted in conformity with its human rights obligations including the prohibition of inhuman and degrading treatment and procedural safeguards set forth in the Refugee Convention, the ECHR and the ICCPR that it was bound by at the time of occurrence of the relevant acts, Serbia is in breach of its international obligations under Articles 12 and 13 ARSIWA.

Attribution of responsibility to the EU (IO) through its implementing partner, in this case EASO and to individual EU Member States in complicity with Serbia

The EU possesses international legal personality, which means that it enjoys international rights and bears international obligations and duties¹³⁶. Therefore, it could be argued that the activities of EASO and of the Member States in the context of operational support to Serbia may trigger the international responsibility of the EU.

The relevant norms are enshrined in ARSIWA and ARIO. There are three main ways to argue the responsibility of the EU during these operations; i) responsibility under Article 7 ARIO, ii) responsibility for complicity under Article 14 ARIO and, iii) responsibility for concerted action under Principle 7 GPSRIL.

¹³⁵ ECtHR (GC) 21 November 2019, 47287/15, *Ilias and Ahmed v Hungary*. See also ECtHR, 12625/17 *Shahzad v. Hungary* 8 July 2021, 64050/16 *W.A. and Others v. Hungary* 15 December 2022, and 59435/17 *Alhowais v Hungary* 2 February 2023.

¹³⁶ Article 47 of the Treaty on European Union (TEU). According to the CJEU, 'in its external relations the Community enjoys the capacity to establish contractual links with third countries'. See: Case 22-70 *Commission of the European Communities v Council of the European Communities, European Agreement on Road Transport*, 31 March 1971, paras 13–14.

Attribution under ILC rules

At a micro-level and considering the direct and immediate consequences of EU involvement, the financial, operational and technical assistance offered by the EU (through its agencies, including EASO) to Serbian authorities has not on its own led to human rights violations as it was aimed at improving existing international standards in terms of protection and reception of refugees on Serbian territory. Serbia's incentive to use this assistance to implement new laws and establish asylum procedures – modelled after the EU asylum acquis, stemmed from Serbia's prospect of accession to the EU. In this context, an argument of legal attribution of responsibility to the EU would be implausible, primarily due to the difficulty of establishing a causal nexus between that cooperation and the wrongful act, as required under ILC rules.

Attribution based on concerted action

In this case, improved asylum and reception standards in Serbia could be said to constitute one aspect of a broader plan by the EU namely, to make Serbia a place for containing migrants. As pointed out in the SERBIA Report, Serbia was trying to adhere to the new standards and simultaneously to address the risk of being confronted with great migration pressures and becoming a migration hotspot or buffer state. In this context, although cooperation with the EU has indeed led to better standards – mainly on paper – it has led to great pressure on Serbia, which in the end was unable to treat the increased number of asylum seekers in its territory in line with national, EU and international standards.

Therefore, it can be argued that violations occurred *because* Serbia operates under framework conditions imposed by its cooperation with the EU, which essentially render it a buffer state and recipient of re-admitted – and pushed back, as explained below – migrants. Under these conditions, even if, in theory, Serbia had the capacity and resources to develop an effective asylum system and to improve the situation for the individuals falling within the scope of its protection system, in practice, it was left with minimal incentives to do so.

Pursuant to the GPSRIL, cooperation between the EU, its Member States and non-EU states in the context of migration control and joint cross-border police activities may give rise to shared responsibility based on concerted action (Principle 7).

As discussed in Section 2.4., in these situations, multiple actors coordinate their conduct with a view to achieving a common aim. The definition of concerted action under Principle 7, paragraph 2, does not require that the goal pursued by two or more international persons is per se in contravention of international law. What is required is that a wrongful act is committed in the course of that concerted action¹³⁷.

¹³⁷ The air strikes conducted in Libya in 2011 by the USA, the UK, France, and Canada, acting through their own organs before NATO took command of the operations, can be considered an example of concerted action. See SC Res. 1973 (2011); S. Erlanger, 'Confusion over Who

In this case, Principle 7 on concerted action might be used to attribute responsibility to the EU. This responsibility would be shared with Serbia and potentially also with those EU Member States contributing funds and operational support, e.g. through EASO, as the wrongful acts pertaining to substandard protection in Serbia have been committed in the course of a concerted action with the common goal of stemming asylum movements to the EU and its Member States.

An element that should be satisfied, in order for responsibility for concerted action to be established under Principle 7, is the actors' 'constructive knowledge' about the circumstances of the internationally wrongful act. The criterion of constructive knowledge is premised on the view that when information is available to actors involved they cannot invoke *ignorance of the circumstances*¹³⁸ when engaged in concerted action. As pointed out in the GPSRIL, the standard of constructive knowledge has been supported by the case law of international courts, where human rights violations had occurred in the context of interstate cooperation¹³⁹. For instance, in the *M.S.S. v Belgium and Greece* case, the ECtHR ruled that Belgian authorities 'knew or ought to have known' about the poor reception conditions and major deficiencies in Greece's asylum procedure, and therefore, they should have suspended the transfer of the applicant to Greece under the Dublin Regulation¹⁴⁰. In light of this, it would not be unthinkable to claim that the EU and its Member States had knowledge of the human rights violations occurring in Serbia and that – even if a harmful outcome was not intended – they expected that it was possible that the harmful outcome would occur as a result of their continued cooperation and financial assistance to Serbian authorities.

6.2 CASE 2: Formal responsibility with respect to human rights violations in the context of border management in Serbia

6.2.1. Wrongful act

The wrongful acts identified in this case of formal responsibility consist of deterrence of migrants through systematic rights violations including of the *non-refoulement* principle (pushbacks) by Serbia and the lack of human rights safeguards in the context of the

Leads Libya Strikes, and for How Long', New York Times (21 March 2011). Another example is the bombing of Iraq carried out by coalition partners, where, although only certain states carried out the actual bombings, multiple other states participated in the decision-making and execution processes. Finally, an example mentioned explicitly in the commentary of Principle 7 is the cooperation between the EU, its Member States and third countries in the context of border management and migration control. See the commentary to Principle 7, para. 7, GPSRIL 46-47.

¹³⁸ See Harriet Moynihan, 'Aiding and Assisting: The Mental Element under Article 16 of the International Law Commission's Articles on State Responsibility', (2018), 67 *International and Comparative Law Quarterly* 461–462.

¹³⁹ See the commentary to Principle 6, para. 5, GPSRIL 42-43.

¹⁴⁰ ECtHR, *M.S.S. v Belgium and Greece*, Appl. no. 30696/09, Judgment of 21 January 2011 para 358.

Integrated Border Management (IBM) Project (financed by the EU Regional Trust Fund in response to the Syrian Crisis, the 'MADAD Fund', and DG ECHO fund and IPA II) and of Frontex Operations in Serbia.

6.2.2. Causation

As suggested earlier, Serbia has been perceiving itself not as a destination country for asylum seekers but rather as a transit country. Between 2015 and 2016 in particular, most migrant and refugee movements from Greece to North Macedonia, as well as from Bulgaria, northwards to Hungary and Croatia, passed through Serbia¹⁴¹. Cooperation with the EU has shaped Serbian migration policy and border management in the direction of preventing refugees from entering the country or confining refugees there. In addition, widespread pushback practices from EU countries to Serbia have triggered further pushbacks from Serbia to other Balkan countries¹⁴².

The EU Member States' pushback practice was a result of the 2016 borders closure following the adoption of the EU-Türkiye Statement. We consider it useful here to distinguish between the various border situations where Serbia is involved:

- Croatian–Serbian border: pushbacks by Croatian authorities to Serbia;
- Hungarian–Serbian border: pushbacks by Hungarian authorities to Serbia and the construction of a fence¹⁴³;
- Romanian–Serbian border: pushbacks by Romanian authorities to Serbia;
- Serbian–North Macedonian border: pushbacks by Serbian authorities to North Macedonia and the construction of a wire fence in the municipality of Preševo in 2020¹⁴⁴;
- Serbian–Bulgarian border: pushbacks by Serbian authorities to Bulgaria.

Pushback practices by Croatia and Hungary to Serbia¹⁴⁵ were very much tolerated by Serbian authorities and condoned by the EU Delegation in Serbia. Serbian authorities, including the Serbian reception agency (KIRS) were providing health care, accommodation, and basic humanitarian aid to persons pushed back via projects financed by the EU (MADAD and IPA), while Serbian authorities were periodically transporting migrants from the northern border areas of the country to the southern parts of Serbia in order to further reduce migration pressures on its EU-Serbia external borders¹⁴⁶.

¹⁴¹ J Abikova and W Piotrowicz, 'Shaping the Balkan Corridor: Development and Changes in the Migration Route 2015–16' (2021) 59(5) *International Migration* 248–65.

¹⁴² SERBIA Report p. 17.

¹⁴³ Hungary completes new anti-migrant border fence with Serbia | Euronews

¹⁴⁴ M Stojanović, 'Na granici Srbije i Makedonije "niče" ograda preko privatnih oranica i livada' (24 August 2022), N1 available at <https://rs.n1info.com/vesti/a632775-na-granici-srbije-i-makedonije-nice-ogradapreko-privatnih-oranica-i-livada/>.

¹⁴⁵ UNHCR, *Serbia inter agency operational update*, July 2016, available at <https://data.unhcr.org/fr/documents/details/49993> accessed 5 February 2023.

¹⁴⁶ SERBIA Report p. 84.

The main attribute of these unlawful pushback practices is that they were conducted outside of any legal procedures (contrary to the EU-Serbian readmission agreement and other bilateral readmission agreements), and that Serbian authorities and EU representatives in Serbia were reportedly aware of such border practice¹⁴⁷. Based on interviews with Serbian officials, Serbian police were either not present on the northern borders or deliberately ignored such systematic unlawful practice¹⁴⁸.

As regards deterrence practices by Serbian authorities southwards, including pushbacks and the construction of a fence, even if these were not conducted under the auspices of or with the use of direct EU financial or operational support, EU institutions have not condemned the practice at the southern Serbian border, or at the border of other EU Member States that had normalised fences and pushbacks¹⁴⁹. Furthermore, access to territory has not been assessed in progress monitoring of the EU accession process¹⁵⁰.

In addition, Frontex officers have been carrying out joint operations on Serbian territory with their Serbian counterparts. In particular, Frontex officers from 14 Member States work with Serbian police officers 'to surveil and protect the border and fight smuggling and organised crime'¹⁵¹. The operation takes place at Serbia's border with Bulgaria, which has seen a rising number of illegal border crossings in recent years. It is coordinated from the Frontex headquarters in Warsaw, Poland while a Local Coordination Centre has been established in the premises of the Gradina Border Crossing Point. Frontex officers assist Serbia in border management, carry out joint operations and deploy teams in the regions of Serbia that border the EU.

Under the Status Agreement between the EU and Serbia¹⁵², which entered into force in May 2021, Frontex launched the 'Joint Operation Serbia - Land 2021' as an important step in the implementation of the Status Agreement¹⁵³. The aim has been to 'provide technical

¹⁴⁷ On this, see the 29/6/2022 letter addressed to the European Commission by Inma VAZQUEZ, Representative of Médecins Sans Frontières to the European Union, where MSF report violent practices against migrants kept in shipping containers in Hungary before being pushed back to Serbia. See also the Commission's response, European Commission Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs, Ref. Ares(2022)7699028 - 08/11/2022.

¹⁴⁸ SERBIA Report p. 26.

¹⁴⁹ Ibid, Lehmann p. 12.

¹⁵⁰ European Commission (October 2021). 'Serbia 2021 Report.' SWD(2021) 288 final, https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/serbia-report-2021_en.

¹⁵¹ <https://Frontex.europa.eu/media-centre/news/news-release/Frontex-expands-presence-in-western-balkans-with-operation-in-serbia-9WRMiW> accessed 2 December 2022.

¹⁵² Status Agreement between the European Union and the Republic of Serbia on actions carried out by the European Border and Coast Guard Agency in the Republic of Serbia ST/15579/2018/REV/1 OJ L 202, 25.6.2020, p. 3-15 available at [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:22020A0625\(01\)&from=EN](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:22020A0625(01)&from=EN) accessed 2 December 2022.

¹⁵³ https://www.statewatch.org/media/2597/20210716_ed-notification-letter_ep_jo-serbia-land-2021.pdf accessed 2 December 2022.

and operational assistance to Serbia by coordinating operational activities at the land borders of Serbia with Bulgaria. The joint operation also aims to tackle cross-border crime originating from the Western Balkan region towards the EU, as well as to control illegal immigration flows and to enhance European cooperation on border guard functions and law-enforcement activities¹⁵⁴.

Article 7 of the Agreement read together with Article 2(f) affords Frontex officers – including both Agency employees and personnel seconded by participating Member States – criminal, civil and administrative immunity from Serbian jurisdiction. Several authors have raised concerns about Frontex's operational role in third countries, including with respect to lack of human rights safeguards¹⁵⁵.

The Agreement has been seen as directly contributing to containment, achieving concrete results in strengthening readmission of migrants in the Western Balkans. According to the Serbian Ministry of Interior, Frontex has directly enabled efficient transfers of third country nationals caught along the Serbian–Bulgarian border to Bulgaria, upon validation of their illegal entry and communication with Bulgarian and Frontex Bulgaria representatives¹⁵⁶.

6.2.3. Responsibility attribution

Attribution of responsibility to Serbia

Border surveillance as well as control of entry to and residence in Serbia rests with its executive organs, and thus the wrongful acts committed on its territory in the context of its close cooperation with the EU to manage refugee movements, are attributable to Serbia under Article 4 ARSIWA. In particular, not having acted in conformity with its human rights obligations regarding the prohibition of *refoulement* and the right to leave as enshrined in the Refugee Convention, the ECHR and the ICCPR, Serbia is in breach of its international obligations under Articles 12 and 13 ARSIWA.

¹⁵⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵⁵ See, among others, Mariana Gkliati and Jane Kilpatrick, 'Frontex cooperation with third countries: examining the human rights implications', (Nov 2021) 68 *Forced Migration Review*, 16-18; Florin Coman-Kund, 'The Cooperation between the European Border and Coast Guard Agency and Third Countries According to the New 'Frontex' Regulation: Legal and Practical Implications in Herwig Hofmann, Ellen Vos & Merijn Chamon (eds), *The External Dimension of EU Agencies and Bodies* (Edward Elgar Publishing 2019).

¹⁵⁶ SERBIA Report p. 85.

It should be noted here that although pushbacks to Bulgaria might be considered, at least in theory, as potentially exposing asylum seekers and refugees to adequate CEAS standards, this does not alter the fact that Serbian authorities were coercively interfering with individual rights, an interference which in several cases has led to violations on the ground¹⁵⁷.

Attribution of responsibility to the EU through its implementing partner Frontex

We note that research – in ASILE reports and beyond – does not indicate strong evidence of fundamental rights violations in joint operations at the Serbian–Bulgarian border. We do regard it plausible, though, that the EU be confronted with relevant responsibility arguments and, hence, it is worth exploring further¹⁵⁸.

As with EASO in CASE 1, it could be argued that the activities of Frontex and of the Member States in the context of joint surveillance operations in Serbia may trigger the international responsibility of the EU. This responsibility would be attributable under Article 7 ARIO, and responsibility for complicity under Article 14 ARIO.

The attribution of conduct to Frontex requires an analysis of both Article 7 ARIO and Article 4 ARSIWA. Article 7 ARIO stipulates that the conduct of ‘a State organ’ that is placed at the disposal of an international organisation is considered as an act of that organisation if the organisation exercises effective control over that conduct. Thus, it is first necessary to establish whether the individuals deployed to joint operations of Frontex can be regarded as organs of the Member States. Article 4 ARSIWA states that ‘the conduct of any State organ shall be considered an act of that State’. Accordingly, the reference to a state organ is intended in the most general sense¹⁵⁹; ‘whether the organ exercises legislative, executive, judicial or any other functions’ as per Article 4 ARSIWA. Since the border guards of the Member States operating in Frontex’s joint operations are

¹⁵⁷ See e.g., Human Rights Watch, *Bulgaria: Pushbacks, Abuse at Borders Halt Summary Returns, Beatings, Robbery of Asylum Seekers* (20 January 2016) available at <https://www.hrw.org/news/2016/01/20/bulgaria-pushbacks-abuse-borders>

¹⁵⁸ For an analysis of responsibility questions in the context of Frontex joint operations in Serbia, see also Julia Kienast, Nikolas Feith Tan and Jens Vedsted-Hansen *EU Third Country Arrangements: Human Rights Compatibility & Attribution of Responsibility* (ASILE, March 2023). In terms of treaty obligations, the authors draw attention to the fact that the ECHR does not govern Frontex operations in Serbia given that the EU is not a party to the Convention, yet the EU Charter binds the activities of EU agencies beyond the territorial area of the Union, p.54-56. For further literature on the matter, see Laura Letourneux, ‘Protecting the Borders from the Outside: An Analysis of the Status Agreements on Actions Carried Out by Frontex Concluded between the EU and Third Countries’ (2022) *European Journal of Migration and Law*, 24(3) p.330-356; Lena Karamanidou and Bernd Kasperek, *Fundamental Rights, Accountability and Transparency in European Governance of Migration: The Case of the European Border and Coast Guard Agency Frontex* (Respond working paper, 2020) and Florin Coman-Kund, ‘The cooperation between the European Border and Coast Guard Agency and third countries according to the new Frontex regulation: Legal and practical implications’, *The external dimension of EU agencies and bodies* (Edward Elgar Publishing 2019).

¹⁵⁹ See ILC ARSIWA, article 4, commentary (6).

generally law-enforcement personnel¹⁶⁰, they are state organs within the meaning of Article 4 ARSIWA, and hence Article 7 ARIO.

Unlike Article 6 ARIO which includes cases where the organ is fully seconded to an organisation, Article 7 ARIO deals with situations where the personnel seconded by a state to an international organisation act 'to a certain extent' as an organ of the seconding state¹⁶¹. The Commentary gives the example of military contingents put at the disposal of the UN for its peacekeeping operations as the state retains disciplinary powers and criminal jurisdiction over them¹⁶². Likewise, members of the teams who are not statutory staff in Frontex's joint operations remain subject to the disciplinary measures of the home Member State, while the statutory staff is subject to those of Frontex¹⁶³. But both operate under the instructions of the host Member State¹⁶⁴. As stated in Article 7, the issue of whether the conduct of the seconded organ is attributable to the receiving organisation is resolved by examining whether it has 'effective control' over the conduct of the seconded organ.

According to the Commentary to Article 7, the criterion for attribution of conduct is based on 'the factual control over the specific conduct taken by the organ or agent placed at the receiving organisation's disposal'¹⁶⁵. This broad formulation is not followed by an articulation of the criteria on the basis of which effective control should be assessed. However, the Commentary refers to ECtHR case law that elaborated on the notion of 'effective control', in particular in cases *Behrami* and *Saramati*. Referring to the 'effective control' criterion under ARIO, the Court held that the decisive factor in these joint cases was whether the UN Security Council 'retained ultimate authority and control so that operational command only was delegated'¹⁶⁶. This 'ultimate authority' and control test

¹⁶⁰ For details, see relevant Agreements <https://prd.Frontex.europa.eu/?form-fields%5Bsearch%5D&form-fields%5Bdate-from%5D&form-fields%5Bdate-to%5D&form-fields%5Bdocument-category%5D%5B0%5D=292&form-fields%5Boffset%5D=0&form-fields%5Bform-post-id%5D=N2QwYTQ2MWJhMWQxNzhYWM0NmQ5NWNkNmViMjgyMjZNVFk0T0E9PTMxNDk4NjUyMDViODVjNDI3NmVmNzdOWYwODJmZGlxYjE4M2JhYmVmNjU2MzczNTAx&form-fields%5Bmodule-post-id%5D=ZmRIYTk1NjkwOWFiYWNmMGZiMGU0ZDRhMTk4MDNmMTBNemt3TVE9PTY4NTE4ODMzMmU5MTIxYWZyY2RkYmE5YTI2N2E1NzZjOTc0NmUyMTAwODM2MzE5MzA1> accessed 2 December 2022.

¹⁶¹ ILC ARIO, article 7, commentary (1).

¹⁶² *Ibid.*

¹⁶³ Regulation (EU) 2019/1896 of 13 November 2019 on the European Border and Coast Guard OJ L 295, 14.11.2019 (hereinafter Frontex Regulation) article 43(5) and (6).

¹⁶⁴ Frontex Regulation, article 43(1).

¹⁶⁵ ILC ARIO, article 7, commentary (4).

¹⁶⁶ ECtHR, 71412/01 *Behrami and Behrami v France* and 78166/01 *Saramati v France, Germany and Norway* 2 May 2007, para. 133.

was applied by the Court in later judgments¹⁶⁷. Following criticism that it allows states to escape international responsibility¹⁶⁸, the Court shifted its approach in *Al-Jedda v United Kingdom*. It ruled that: ‘the UN Security Council had neither effective control nor ultimate authority and control over the acts and omissions of troops within the Multinational Force’ and attributed Mr Al-Jedda’s detention to the UK and not to the UN¹⁶⁹. Following the same line of reasoning, the ILC notes that in assessing effective control, ‘operational’ control seems more significant than ‘ultimate’ control since the latter hardly implies a role in the act in question¹⁷⁰. Considering the ILC Commentary and its reference to ECtHR’s jurisprudence, the attribution of conduct of the board guards to Frontex requires an evaluation of ‘factual control over the specific conducts’ of the deployed team members, namely the command and control structure during operations.

Based on the Frontex Regulation, border guards perform their tasks during the deployment of the teams through the instructions of the host Member State¹⁷¹, which must be according to the operational plan¹⁷². In this regard, despite the operational plan being drafted by Frontex through its executive director, to be agreed upon by the host Member State and other participating Member States¹⁷³, it is nevertheless the host Member State that issues instructions during the operations. At this point, it is worth noting that through its coordinating officer, Frontex also monitors the correct implementation of the operational plan¹⁷⁴. Furthermore, if the instructions do not comply with the operational plan, Frontex communicates its views to the host Member State regarding the instructions given by it via the coordinating officer and these views must be followed ‘to the extent possible’ by the host Member State¹⁷⁵. Frontex still cannot issue instructions to the personnel deployed during operations, hence it has no role in the chain of command. While the views of Frontex have the capacity to substantially affect the instructions given by the host Member State, they still cannot qualify as instructions that

¹⁶⁷ See ECtHR 6974/05 *Kasumaj v. Greece* 5 July 2007 and 36357/04 *Beric and Others v. Bosnia and Herzegovina* 16 October 2007. For a detailed analysis see Roberta Mungianu, *Frontex and Non-Refoulement: The International Responsibility of the EU* (Cambridge University Press 2016) 65.

¹⁶⁸ See among others Marko Milanović and Tatjana Papić, ‘As Bad As It Gets: The European Court of Human Rights’ *Behrami and Saramati* Decision and General International Law’ (2009) 58(2) *International and Comparative Law Quarterly* 267.

¹⁶⁹ ECtHR, 27021/08 *Al-Jedda v The United Kingdom* 7 July 2011, para .84.

¹⁷⁰ ILC ARIIO, article 7, commentary (10).

¹⁷¹ Frontex Regulation, article 43(1).

¹⁷² The operational plan is binding and covers all necessary aspects for carrying out the operation, including the division of tasks, allocation of responsibilities, the composition of the teams, and command and control provisions. See Frontex Regulation, article 38(3)(d)-(f).

¹⁷³ Frontex Regulation, article 38(2).

¹⁷⁴ Frontex Regulation, article 22.

¹⁷⁵ Frontex Regulation, article 43 (2).

the team members must follow. This is also true for the statutory staff deployed as members of the teams with their executive powers¹⁷⁶.

Considering the above, it could be argued that Frontex does not possess effective control over the conduct of teams deployed during joint operations within the meaning of Article 7 ARIO, thus their conduct cannot be attributed to Frontex, and, by extension, the EU¹⁷⁷.

The fact, however, that the acts above are neither attributable to Frontex nor to the EU, does not preclude an argument for the responsibility of the host EU Member States involved in Frontex operations.

Attribution of conduct to the EU for complicity

The EU's responsibility may be engaged for the acts of team members in joint operations if the EU is found to be complicit with the wrongful conduct of the team members. Article 16 ARSIWA provides that 'a State which aids or assists another State in the commission of an internationally wrongful act by the latter is internationally responsible for doing so if: (a) that State does so with knowledge of the circumstances of the internationally wrongful act; and (b) the act would be internationally wrongful if committed by that State'.

Article 14 ARIO was modelled after Article 16 ARSIWA, albeit referring to international organisations as the aiding or assisting entity. For this reason, our analysis of international responsibility for complicity will be based on Article 16 ARSIWA, applied by analogy to Article 14 ARIO¹⁷⁸.

For aid or assistance to trigger the derivative responsibility of the EU in the context of the surveillance activities of Frontex when supporting Serbian guards, the following elements need to be satisfied: i) aid or assistance, ii) nexus between the aid or assistance and the concerned internationally wrongful act, iii) the mental element of knowledge, and iv) opposability.

What constitutes 'aid or assistance' is a contested issue. The Commentary states that '[there] is no requirement that the aid or assistance should have been essential to the performance of the internationally wrongful act; it is sufficient if it *contributed significantly* to the internationally wrongful act¹⁷⁹. Certain acts including providing materials, training of personnel, technical assistance, and financial or logistical support have been seen as qualifying as 'aid or assistance'. At the same time, mere

¹⁷⁶ Frontex Regulation, article 54. Even though the 2019 Frontex Regulation established Standing Corps with their executive powers, it is still the host Member State that has control over their conduct as well as executive powers during joint operations via its instructions.

¹⁷⁷ For similar arguments, see Melanie Fink, *Frontex and Human Rights: Responsibility in 'Multi-Actor Situations' under the ECHR and EU Public Liability Law* (Oxford University Press 2019) ,136-8; Mungianu, 68-70.

¹⁷⁸ See Helmut P. Aust, *Complicity and the Law of State Responsibility* (Cambridge University Press 2011) 3.

¹⁷⁹ ILC ARSIWA, article 16, commentary (5).

encouragement, moral support or approval in a political forum is regarded as not amounting to aid or assistance under the ILC norms¹⁸⁰. According to Aust, it would not be conceptually productive to adopt a list of 'typical cases' of aid or assistance¹⁸¹, and thus, the provision is better seen as open-ended in nature and interpreted dynamically. In addition, although it is not clear-cut whether 'aid or assistance' can take the form of omissions, drawing on the ICJ Genocide Convention case, Aust claims that it is not inconceivable to establish complicity through omission¹⁸².

With respect to the 'nexus' requirement, Article 16 ARSIWA is considered to be limited to those cases where the aid or assistance given is 'clearly linked' to the subsequent wrongful conduct.¹⁸³ In other words, there has to be a nexus between the aid or assistance and the wrongful conduct¹⁸⁴. This, in conjunction with the fact that aid or assistance does not require an essential contribution to the wrongful act may lead to the conclusion that a rigid cause-and-effect analysis is not required here¹⁸⁵ but rather that some 'causative connection'¹⁸⁶ would suffice. It is implausible that Article 16 would cover 'aid or assistance' only remotely or 'indirectly' related to an internationally wrongful act¹⁸⁷.

With respect to the mental element, Article 16(a) ARSIWA requires that the assisting state has 'knowledge of the circumstances'. Therefore, an assisting state is responsible if it is aware of the circumstances of the internationally wrongful act committed by the assisted state. The Commentary, however, narrows the textual meaning by adding an element of intent, holding that 'aid or assistance must be given in order to facilitate the commission of the wrongful conduct' and that there is no responsibility 'unless the relevant State

¹⁸⁰ Georg Nolte and Helmut P Aust, 'Equivocal Helpers-Complicit States, Mixed Messages and International Law' (2009), 58(1) *International and Comparative Law Quarterly* 13. See also: Harriet Moynihan, 'Aiding and Assisting: Challenges in Armed Conflict and Counterterrorism' (2016) Chatham House Research Paper <https://www.chathamhouse.org/sites/default/files/publications/research/2016-11-11-aiding-assisting-challenges-armed-conflict-moynihan.pdf> accessed 1 December 2022.

¹⁸¹ Ibid Aust, 200.

¹⁸² Ibid Aust 230. See also Miles Jackson, *Complicity in International Law* (Oxford University Press 2015), 156–58; and Vladyslav Lanovoy, 'Complicity in an Internationally Wrongful Act' in André Nollkaemper and Ilias Plakokefalos (eds), *Principles of Shared Responsibility in International Law: An Appraisal of the State of the Art* (Cambridge University Press 2014), 149. For a different view see James Crawford, *State Responsibility: The General Part* (Cambridge University Press 2013), 403.

¹⁸³ ILC, 'ARSIWA', article 16, commentary (5). See also Nolte and Aust, 10.

¹⁸⁴ Richard M Scott, 'State Responsibility for Complicity in the Internationally Wrongful Acts of Non-State Armed Groups' (2016) 24(2), *Journal of Conflict and Security Law*, 387.

¹⁸⁵ Ibid Lanovoy, 161.

¹⁸⁶ Ibid Moynihan 2016, 8.

¹⁸⁷ Ibid Nolte and Aust, 10. See also Christine Chinkin, *Third Parties in International Law* (Clarendon Press 1993), 297.

organ intended to facilitate the occurrence of the internationally wrongful conduct'¹⁸⁸. As Nolte and Aust put it 'with a view to facilitating' implies a requirement of 'wrongful intent'¹⁸⁹. In the Genocide Convention case, applying Article 16 ARSIWA by analogy, the ICJ ruled that providing aid or assistance cannot be treated as complicity to the crime of genocide unless 'at the least' that organ or person acted knowingly, that is to say, it was aware of the specific intent (*dolus specialis*) of the principal perpetrator¹⁹⁰. In light of this, Nolte and Aust argue that, in principle, more than mere knowledge is required¹⁹¹.

Having said this, the authors caution against interpreting this as allowing states to deny responsibility for complicity in situations where internationally wrongful acts are manifestly being committed. State A regularly provides support to State B to cope with migration and refugee movements in its territory and it is obvious that State B is systematically violating human rights with the help of this support. If State A learns of the commission of those violations and continues to offer support, it begins to share the specific intent of State B to violate human rights in the course of migration control. In that sense, lack of intent can, in some cases, be offset by sufficient knowledge¹⁹².

Along the same lines, there is much scepticism towards the intent requirement for making 'the whole concept of complicity unworkable'¹⁹³, while it is held that 'giving greater weight to the textual meaning of the articles where there are discrepancies with the commentary reflects the detailed attention that the ILC paid to the adoption of the articles'¹⁹⁴.

The final requirement for establishing derivative responsibility is laid out in Article 16(b) ARSIWA which requires that 'the act would be internationally wrongful if committed by the assisting State'. According to the Commentary, it is necessary for the responsibility of an assisting state that the conduct in question would have constituted a breach of its own international obligations. The logic behind this is that 'a State cannot do by another what it cannot do by itself'¹⁹⁵. Except in cases where the breach pertains to a customary international law rule, this is a limiting factor considering that international organisations are, by and large, not parties to human rights treaties.

In light of the above, it is arguable that Frontex's organising and coordinating roles in the context of its surveillance activities may amount to 'aid or assistance'. Surveillance

¹⁸⁸ ARSIWA article 16, commentary (5).

¹⁸⁹ Ibid Nolte and Aust, 14. See also Jackson, 160.

¹⁹⁰ The Genocide Convention case, [421].

¹⁹¹ Ibid Nolte and Aust, 14.

¹⁹² Ibid Nolte and Aust, 15.

¹⁹³ Bernhard Graefrath, 'Complicity in the law of international responsibility', (1996) 2 *Revue Belge de Droit International* 375.

¹⁹⁴ Giorgio Gaja, 'Interpreting Articles Adopted by the International Law Commission' (2015,85(1) *British Yearbook of International Law* 20.

¹⁹⁵ ILC, ARSIWA, article 16, commentary (6).

activities through which the Serbian authorities detect migrants moving to Serbia can be considered as a 'significant contribution' to the commission of human rights violations by the Serbian authorities. Therefore, the surveillance activities qualify as aid or assistance within the meaning of Article 14 ARIO. In addition, it could be argued that the requirement of the link (nexus) between these acts of aid or assistance and internationally wrongful acts committed by Serbian authorities seems to be fulfilled. Arguably, some degree of causal relation exists between the aid in the form of surveillance support on the one hand, and the interception and pullback of migrants by Serbian authorities on the other. To put it simply, it would not be possible for the Serbian authorities to detect and locate migrants at the border without the surveillance support by Frontex.

Even the knowledge requirement is arguably fulfilled. Frontex is responsible for drawing up the operational plans and monitoring its implementation through its executive director¹⁹⁶ and it has a clear picture of the operation and the performance of surveillance activities by the team members. In addition, the situation at the borders is well-documented by various organisations, NGOs and other commentators, and thus it could be argued that the EU, through Frontex, is likely to possess the knowledge of the commission of the internationally wrongful acts against migrants in and out of Serbia (knowledge of the concrete risk of human rights violations and acceptance through continued cooperation). Finally, the question of whether both the EU and Serbia are bound by the same obligation can be answered in the affirmative, particularly in cases where the breached international obligations implicate the right to life, right to asylum, the prohibition of *refoulement*, and the prohibition of collective expulsions.

The above considered, Frontex's surveillance operations in the form of aid or assistance during its joint operations with Serbia may amount to the formal attributability of relevant human rights violations to the EU under Article 14 ARIO.

6.3. CASE 3: Systemic responsibility with respect to the containment of refugee movements in Serbia

6.3.1. Wrongful act

The wrongful acts identified in this case of systemic responsibility attribution consist of violations of the right to leave, the right to seek asylum, the right to effective remedies, and the prohibition of torture and inhumane and degrading treatment, with the closure of the Western Balkan route.

6.3.2. Causation

As detailed above, negotiations between the EU and Serbia resulted in the introduction of several measures in the Serbian system (such as the asylum border procedure, different types of residence, IBM system of border control, concept of blocking migration).

¹⁹⁶ Frontex Regulation, article 22.

The starting point of these negotiations has been the Western Balkans Route Leaders Statement of 2015¹⁹⁷, a political instrument expressing commitment of the EU and non-EU Western Balkan route countries to cooperate on addressing migration challenges. The Statement was followed by two meetings in Vienna and Zagreb, on 24 and 28 February 2016, marking the starting point of the coordinated closure of the Western Balkan route and the introduction of limitations to the movement of various national groups of migrants. This coincided with the signing of the EU-Türkiye deal, reflecting a pattern of policy response with the aim of containing refugee movements originating from Syria.

The closure of the formalised, state-facilitated Western Balkan corridor¹⁹⁸ left refugees and asylum seekers in Europe with no choice but to move irregularly, becoming victims of abuse at the hands of both smugglers and border authorities (of EU states, of Serbia), including through pushbacks¹⁹⁹.

As one expert interviewee in the SERBIA Report emphasised: 'With the buffer zone established in Serbia and/or in other Balkan non-EU countries, influx of irregular migrants to EU would reduce to only a few in need of international protection, all others would eventually be stranded in the Balkans'²⁰⁰.

Although the EU has been advocating for formalisation in the asylum context, EU-Serbia cooperation has been informal. For instance, by tolerating migrants' *de facto* irregular position, authorities in Serbia, including camp management and the police, strongly encouraged migrants to keep looking for opportunities to (irregularly) enter the EU²⁰¹. In that sense, informality as in staying outside legal procedures and invisible to the system offered a way to escape containment.

6.3.3. Responsibility attribution

Attribution under ILC rules

Although the financial instruments were meant to help Serbia cope with the humanitarian crisis in its territory, they have essentially ensured that refugees and asylum seekers are contained there, alleviating pressures for EU countries at the EU's external borders. In that sense, financial responsibility of the EU for financing border management in Serbia might be arguable, together with political responsibility. However, the EU's role in EU-Serbia cooperation has remained at the level of technical and financial support, and no

¹⁹⁷ <https://www.refworld.org/pdfid/563216cb4.pdf> accessed 5 February 2023.

¹⁹⁸ European Union. (25 October 2015). 'Leaders' Meeting on Refugee Flows along the Western Balkans Route: Leaders' Statement'. 25 October 2015, www.refworld.org/docid/563216cb4.html.

¹⁹⁹ On this see Julian M. Lehmann, *Borders, money, and a B&B – Policy drivers on the Global Compact on Refugees in Serbia* (ASILE October 2022) p. 6, available at <https://www.asileproject.eu/4599-2/>

²⁰⁰ SERBIA Report p. 83.

²⁰¹ SERBIA Report p. 84.

direct involvement of the EU or its partners in alleged human rights violations can be established. Thus, it is rather hard for the requirements for formal responsibility attribution to be fulfilled, primarily due to evidentiary problems.

Attribution based on concerted action

In this case, where formal attribution of an internationally wrongful act to the EU is technically impossible under ILC rules, it is plausible to argue attribution on the basis of concerted action under GPSRIL. Let us imagine the following scenario:

Person A, contained in Serbia, has suffered an injury within the meaning of Principle 1.c GPSRIL. That injury is indivisible (see GPSRIL Commentary as discussed in Section 2.2.). There is no single wrongful act causing it; Containment is an agreed goal of the cooperating states (Serbia and EU Member States) and the EU, and their cooperation qualifies as concerted action under Principle 7 GPSRIL, entailing attribution to cooperating states and the EU.

Following this line of reasoning, a systemic approach to responsibility attribution focuses on the wider involvement of the EU and its Member States in migration governance in Serbia. Similar to Türkiye and Tunisia, the EU has shaped Serbian migration and border policy in the direction of preventing refugees from entering the country (deterrence) or keeping refugees there (containment), which has resulted in systematic violations of migrant rights, as emphasised in the SERBIA Report. Arguably, this form of hypercomplex cooperation has been chosen by the EU and its Member States with (direct) intent to evade attribution under ILC rules.

7. Niger

Cases of responsibility for Niger

7.1. CASE 1: Formal responsibility with respect to substandard protection and reception in Niger

7.1.1. Wrongful act

The wrongful acts identified in this case of formal responsibility attribution consist of human rights violations as a result of deficiencies in asylum procedures and reception conditions in Niger following the implementation of the 2017 Emergency Transit Mechanism (ETM).

7.1.2. Causation

Niger is a transit country to Libya and Algeria and onwards to the Central Mediterranean. Since 2015, EU efforts to combat irregular migration from the African continent have resulted in close cooperation with Niger. EU involvement in Niger has been formalised under the EU Emergency Trust fund for Africa (EUTF)²⁰², launched at the 2015 Valetta summit²⁰³, as well as technical assistance for the operationalisation of the National Borders Policy 2019-2035²⁰⁴. Although the strategic agenda laid down at the 2015 Valetta summit foresees addressing 'root causes of migration' and enhanced cooperation on legal migration, EU priorities in Niger are geared towards the securitisation of migration in the form of border management, effectively tasking the country to police and prevent onward migration to Europe²⁰⁵.

²⁰² Commission Decision C(2015)7293 of 20 October 2015 on the establishment of a European Union Emergency Trust Fund for stability and addressing root causes of irregular migration and displaced persons in Africa. For a detailed analysis, see Thomas Spijkerboer and Elies Steyger, 'European External Migration Funds and Public Procurement Law' (2019) 4 European papers 493. For details see https://ec.europa.eu/trustfundforafrica/content/about_en accessed 6 February 2023.

²⁰³ <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/meetings/international-summit/2015/11/11-12/> accessed 6 February 2023.

²⁰⁴ Republique du Niger Ministere le l'interieur, le la Securite Publique, de la Decentralisation et des Affaires Coutumieres et Religieuses (2018) Projet de Document de Politique Nationale des Frontières 2019-2035 <https://www.migration-spccm.ne/fr/documents_strategiques>.

²⁰⁵ See Christophe Chatelot, 'Le Niger, sous-traitant africain de la politique migratoire de l'Europe', Le Monde Afrique 28 juin 2018. For an academic analysis see, among others, Fransje Molenaar, 'Irregular migration and human smuggling networks in Niger' (2017) CRU Report, Clingendael Institut; Daria Davitti and Anca-Elena Ursu, 'Why Securitising the Sahel Will Not Stop Migration' FMU Policy Brief No. 02/2018 (2018) Human Rights Law Centre, University of Nottingham; Florence Boyer et Pascaline Chappart, 'Les frontières européennes

A key component of this securitisation approach has been the implementation of the ETM for the evacuation of vulnerable refugees and asylum seekers from detention in Libya to Niger. The programme's establishment is based on a Memorandum of Understanding signed between the Nigerien Minister of the Interior and the UNHCR Country Representative 'in order to facilitate the processing of refugees and asylum seekers trapped in detention and to ensure access to protection and to durable solutions'²⁰⁶.

The overall objective of actions in the framework of the ETM funded by the EUTF has been 'to strengthen the governance of migration in the region and provide protection and sustainable solutions for migrants and refugees along the Central Mediterranean route'. In particular, the EUTF supports UNCHR's objective, namely, to provide 'emergency protection' in the framework of ETM, as well as 'support to resettlement and complementary pathways for persons in need of international protection' where needed. In addition, it supports IOM in enabling 'assisted voluntary return of vulnerable and stranded migrants in target countries' and 'improve the reintegration of returning migrants in a dignified and sustainable manner'²⁰⁷.

To facilitate the reception of evacuees in Niger, the IOM has been running transit centres in Agadez, Arlit, Dirkou, Niamey where candidates for 'voluntary' return are identified²⁰⁸.

au Niger' (2018) 83 *Vacarme*, pp. 92-98; Tsion Tadesse Abebe, 'Securitisation of Migration in Africa: The Case of Agadez in Niger' (2019) *Africa Report 20*, Institute for Security Studies; Thomas Spijkerboer, 'The New Borders of Empire: European Migration Policy and Domestic Passenger Transport in Niger' in Paul Minderhoud, Sandra Mantu & Karin Zwaan (eds), *Caught in Between Borders: Citizens, migrants and humans. Liber Amicorum in Honour of prof. dr. Elspeth Guild*, Wolf Legal Publishers, Tilburg 2019, pp. 49-57; Leonie Ansems de Vries and Elspeth Guild, 'Seeking Refuge in Europe: Spaces of Transit and the Violence of Migration Management' (2019) 45(12) *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies* 2156-2166; Julia Van Dessel, 'International Delegation and Agency in the Externalization Process of EU Migration and Asylum Policy: the Role of the IOM and the UNHCR in Niger' (2019) 21 *European Journal of Migration and Law* 435; Florence Boyer, 'Sécurité, développement, protection. Le triptyque de l'externalisation des politiques migratoires au Niger' (2019) *Hérodote*, 172(1) p. 171–191; Sébastien Moretti, 'Transit Migration in Niger: Stemming the Flows of Migrants, but at What Cost?' (2020) 3(1) *Migration and Society* 80-88; Philippe M. Frowd, 'Producing the 'transit' migration state: international security intervention in Niger' (2020) 41(2) *Third World Quarterly* 340-358; Morten Bøås, 'EU migration management in the Sahel: unintended consequences on the ground in Niger?' (2021) 42(1) *Third World Quarterly* 52-67.

²⁰⁶ UNHCR, Emergency Transit Mechanism, Factsheet May 2021 available at <https://reporting.unhcr.org/sites/default/files/Niger%20ETM%20Factsheet%20May%202021.pdf> accessed on 6 Feb 2023.

²⁰⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/trustfundforafrica/region/sahel-lake-chad/regional/protection-and-sustainable-solutions-migrants-and-refugees-along_en accessed 6 February 2023.

²⁰⁸ See e.g. ' "Life is a fight that should be fought" Life in transit: Voices from returning migrants', 2019 NIGER Report (Part Two), XCHANGE Research on Migration, p. 9 available at <http://xchange.org/wp-content/uploads/Xchange-Foundation-Niger-Report-Part-Two.pdf> accessed 6 February 2023.

Together with the Nigerien government, the UNHCR established an office of international protection in Agadez in 2017 with a view to identifying asylum needs and providing emergency protection. It is primarily through EU funding that this office and, by extension, the reception and RSD system in Niger has been sustained, to ensure access to asylum 'without resorting to the hazardous journey northwards'²⁰⁹. Furthermore, the UNHCR was responsible for selecting resettlement candidates for the Global North from among refugees²¹⁰. In the past, being granted refugee status in Niger allowed legal residence, close to equal rights with nationals, and basic health care; however, there were minimal employment prospects given that Niger has been classified as one of the least developed countries²¹¹. With the introduction of the ETM and the UNCHR's involvement, resettlement, albeit scarce, became a lawful means to reach the Global North safely from Niger. In that sense, asylum in Niger was primarily a provisional solution until a durable solution could be found.

Although the EU has been pushing for formalisation in the asylum context, it is worth emphasising that a lack of transparency is evident in its cooperation with Niger. This includes the ETM MoU which has not been made available online, the actual role of the UNHCR and the IOM involved in the process, as well as the involvement of national and other international actors criticised for not having introduced appropriate monitoring procedures²¹².

However, several human rights violations have been reported in the context of the ETM implementation²¹³, with reports of dire living conditions on Nigerien soil as a result of food and water shortages, which have increased the risk of diseases, such as malaria, in the Hamdallaye centre²¹⁴.

²⁰⁹ UNHCR, 2017b, 'UNHCR Niger: Mixed Migration Factsheet --Asylum seekers, refugees and migration in Niger', 15 May, p. 2 available at <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/56591.pdf> accessed 6 February 2023.

²¹⁰ Florence Boyer et Pascaline Chappart, 'Les enjeux de la protection au Niger. Les nouvelles impasses politiques du 'transit'?' (2018) *Mouvements*, 30 juin.

²¹¹ United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), 2018, Human Development Index Niger 2018 available at <http://hdr.undp.org/en/countries/profiles/NER> accessed 6 February 2023.

²¹² NIGER Report.

²¹³ A number of shortcomings have been reported in, e.g. the transit centres run by IOM in Agadez and other towns, see <https://alarmephonesahara.info/en/blog/posts/iom-in-niger-criticism-of-serious-shortcomings-in-the-care-of-people-stranded-in-niger> accessed 6 February 2023.

²¹⁴ Bachirou Ayouba Tinni, Abdoulaye Hamadou and Thomas Spijkerboer Country Report Niger WP5. Country Reports (hereinafter NIGER Report) p. 47 https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/D5.2_WP5-Niger-Country-Report-Final.pdf accessed 26 April 2023.

7.1.3. Responsibility attribution

Attribution of responsibility to Niger

The operation of the asylum system in Niger lies with its executive organs, and thus any wrongful acts committed on its territory in the context of the ETM implementation are attributable to Niger under Article 4 ARSIWA.

Attribution of responsibility to the EU (IO) and to individual EU Member States in complicity with Niger, the UNHCR and countries of resettlement

EU–Niger cooperation has resulted in the emergence of several new rules and institutions ultimately determined by the EU. In fact, Niger has adopted a rigorous legal framework relating to migration through an unprecedented legislative and regulatory process over 5 years²¹⁵.

Attribution under ILC rules

At a micro-level, similar to the Serbian case argued above, financial assistance from the EU has strengthened the capacity of the Nigerien authorities in the field of asylum, both in terms of staff and training²¹⁶. The legal instruments introduced in the Nigerien legal order following the ETM have not themselves led to human rights violations, aimed as they were at improving existing national standards in terms of protection and reception of refugees on Nigerien soil. In this context, an argument of legal attribution of formal responsibility to the EU would be implausible, primarily due to the difficulty in establishing a causation between that cooperation and the wrongful act, as required under ILC norms.

The situation is equally complex when it comes to the UNHCR and its involvement in the RSD procedures in Niger. As a result of the poor selection process in Libya²¹⁷, a significant number of claims for international protection by evacuees –determined before they could access resettlement or complementary pathways to Europe and North America – have been rejected²¹⁸. Rejected asylum seekers blamed UNHCR for bringing them into a country they had never considered seeking refuge in and putting them in a limbo situation. According to Lambert, one of them said: ‘UNHCR brought us here. UNHCR is playing with us. We can’t do anything’²¹⁹. It should be noted that initially, the UNHCR was

²¹⁵ As Hamadou puts it, Niger adopted more legal texts relating to migration from 2010 to 2018 than from its independence (in 1960) to 2010. See Abdoulaye Hamadou ‘La gestion des flux migratoires au Niger entre engagements et contraintes’ (2018) 14 *Revue des droits de l’homme*, p. 11.

²¹⁶ NIGER Report.

²¹⁷ On corruption and identification issues see Amara Markous, *Humanitarian Action and Anti-migration Paradox: A case study of UNHCR and IOM in Libya*, (2019) Master’s thesis CERAH Genève, 26f <https://drive.google.com/file/d/17N2EIPWyt-mLO6zyri74FLOuRRRyOU5/view> accessed 6 February 2023.

²¹⁸ Laura Lambert, ‘Extraterritorial asylum processing: the Libya-Niger Emergency Transit Mechanism’ (2021) *Forced Migration Review* 68 on Externalisation p. 19.

²¹⁹ *Ibid* Lambert 2021 p. 20.

only responsible for preparing asylum files and for issuing recommendations in relation to asylum claims within the ETM, and Niger was taking the asylum decisions. In June 2018, the UNHCR negotiated an amendment with the Minister for the Interior that, in case of a resettlement country's readiness, ETM cases could be resettled before they received a Nigerien refugee status²²⁰. If the UNHCR were to reject an application, Niger would be responsible for the asylum decision, as it is the host state that has the capacity to regularise the status of evacuees or to deport them.

As reported via several sources, UNHCR's influence on the asylum adjudication process in Niger increased significantly within the ETM. Training and provision of COI information aside, the UNHCR also recruited, funded, trained and supervised case workers for the Commission nationale d'éligibilité au statut des réfugiés (CNE)²²¹ office in Niamey and Agade., This has essentially transformed the UNHCR from an adviser to a decision-making body²²². In her ethnographic research, Lambert reports that, in the process of 'remaking' asylum in Niger

'state agents were confronted with a considerable loss in discretionary power. In core tasks for the pilot project ETM, the three state committees for asylum adjudication, first instance appeal and the ETM implementation were surprisingly powerless. This was the case for the asylum adjudication, the number of evacuees, and the regulation of entry and stay in Niger, where instead of the bureaucrats, their government or the UNHCR took practical decisions'²²³.

In an attempt to resolve the problem of rejected asylum applicants, the Nigerien Minister for the Interior decided to grant refugee status to all of the appeal cases so they would be resettled and leave Niger. That, however, was seen as contravening the UNHCR's principle that only refugees also recognised by the UN agency are submitted for resettlement. As a result, Niger had to assume responsibility for these people, therefore making their onward movement more difficult. Another related issue concerns the decision on the number of evacuees that would be transferred to Niger. Although a threshold was established with the MoU, the Minister for the Interior and the UNHCR lifted the

²²⁰ Niger, UNHCR, 2018, Avenant N°1 à l'accord entre le Gouvernement de la République du Niger et le Haut Commissariat des Nations unies pour les Réfugiés sur l'instauration d'un Mécanisme d'Évacuation d'urgence et de transit de la Libye vers le Niger, Niamey, 18 June.

²²¹ National Refugee Eligibility Commission, responsible for asylum decision-making established in 2001 in Niger.

²²² Lambert refers to how one CNE member perceived of UNCHR's role in the ETM:

'[Before] it was like a technical counselling. Well, now it is their business, they are running it. Even when it needs whatever, it is them. Until now, it is them who initiate, they receive the people, because we cannot afford to interview people. Especially in the case of the Eritreans and others who only understand their own language. So the UNHCR does everything. The very asylum file is created by the UNHCR.' Lambert 2020 p. 91.

²²³ Ibid, Lambert 2020 p. 96.

threshold without formally amending the MoU²²⁴. Even that number was exceeded.²²⁵ When members of the ETM committee voiced concerns that agreements and principles should not be disrespected, the UNHCR replied that ‘this is an emergency’²²⁶.

The situation described above raises questions of sovereignty and the rule of law. Based on the expanding power of the UNHCR in co-running the asylum system in Niger, an argument in favour of attributing responsibility to Niger (for delegating decision-making power to the UNHCR for the implementation of the ETM) in complicity with the UNHCR (for being in charge of the asylum procedures and reception of ETM evacuees in Niger) under Articles 6 and 14 ARIO could be entertained. It should be noted, though, that unlike the case of UNHCR’s involvement in Tunisia’s asylum policy discussed in Section 5.1.3., the exact involvement of the UNHCR in concrete harmful outcomes would be hard to establish in this case.

Attribution based on concerted action

The support provided by the EU to operationalise the ETM – promoted as a life-saving solution to torture and exploitation of asylum seekers and refugees in Libya – has, indeed, led to improved standards for refugees and asylum seekers in Niger in terms of housing and health care²²⁷. However, improved asylum and reception standards in Niger as well as resettlement arrangements, have shaped Nigerien migration policy: evacuated migrants from Libya are now confined on Nigerien soil: refugees are identified and provided with immediate protection to prevent onward movement and to alleviate pressures on EU countries.

As stated by Cochetel, ‘[r]efugee evacuations can only be part of broader asylum-building and migration management efforts to address the complex movement of migrants and refugees along the Mediterranean routes’²²⁸. There is absolutely no doubt that the implementation of the ETM has led to a situation of great pressure on Niger, which has been essentially transformed into a migration hotspot or buffer state, unable to treat the increased number of asylum seekers found in its territory in line with national, EU and international standards.

²²⁴ Ibid Lambert 2020 p. 92.

²²⁵ UNHCR, Country Operation Update Niger, 2019 Report available at <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/69587> accessed 6 February 2023.

²²⁶ EU Commission, 2019, Progress Report on the Implementation of the European Agenda on Migration, COM(2019) 481 final.

²²⁷ Ibid; UNCHR Factsheet 2021 and <https://airdinternational.org/improved-housing-for-refugees-in-hamdallaye-niger-provides-a-collective-sigh-of-relief/> accessed 6 Feb 2023.

²²⁸ <https://www.refworld.org/cgi-bin/texis/vtx/rwmain?page=search&docid=5a339c604&skip=0&query=evacuation%20mechanism#hit3> accessed 6 Feb 2023.

Lambert points out that increased migration control in the region, continuous violence in Libya, and the ETM with its resettlement programme ‘have multiplied the individual asylum applications in Niger from a few dozen per year to almost 4 000 in 2018’²²⁹.

In light of the above, the GPSRIL (Principle 7) might be used to attribute responsibility to the EU, Niger and the UNHCR for engaging in concerted wrongful action in the context of migration control and joint cross-border activities: the EU by contributing with funds to the implementation of the ETM; Niger by condoning externally imposed policies and not properly receiving and protecting migrants and refugees on its territory; and the UNCHR for taking over the asylum adjudication with adverse effects for the applicants. An argument could also be made for the shared responsibility of resettlement countries for their active involvement in asylum adjudication cases in Niger, in cooperation with the UNHCR²³⁰, and for essentially sustaining a system like the ETM whose aim has been to resettle evacuees from Libya in Global North countries. In the face of increasing migration control and border violence, the possibility – albeit scarce – to reach countries in the Global North safely from Niger has contributed to an environment where asylum seekers were ‘stuck’ in despair waiting for their asylum decisions, under the constant threat of deportation to countries where they feared renewed human rights violations²³¹. It is telling that asylum in Niger in the pre-ETM era, entailed a legal residence status to which a set of equal rights were attached. Whereas in the context of ETM, filing an asylum application was serving as a provisional solution in a precarious and violent context²³².

To summarise, the wrongful acts pertaining to living conditions and asylum procedures in Niger have been committed in the course of a concerted action aiming at immobilising sub-Saharan refugees in Niger and at controlling mobility to the EU and to countries in the Global North, including EU Member States. Through such concerted action, the actors involved were able to produce results that they could not have brought about on their own.

To visualise this, we could imagine the following cases:

Table 3: Niger attribution based on concerted action

Actors in concerted action	EU	Niger	UNHCR	Countries of resettlement

²²⁹ Laura Lambert, ‘Who is doing asylum in Niger? State bureaucrats’ perspectives and strategies on the externalisation of refugee protection’ (2020) 51 *Anthropologie & développement*. It is worth noting that the recognition rate in Niger in 2007 was at 45.5% based on the report by Florianne Charrière and Marion Frésia, ‘West Africa as a Migration and Protection Area’, (2008) UNHCR/European Union, 31.

²³⁰ *Ibid*, Lambert 2020 p. 93.

²³¹ *Ibid*.

²³² *Ibid* p. 89.

Contribution to indivisible harm	EUTF financing the ETM	Not respecting asylum seekers rights in terms of reception and access to fair and effective remedies	Running the RSD procedures	Involvement in RSD procedures in the context of the ETM and pledging resettlement places for ETM asylum seekers
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7.2. CASE 2: Formal responsibility with respect to human rights violations in the context of border management in Niger

7.2.1. Wrongful act

The wrongful acts identified in this case of formal responsibility attribution consist of the deterrence of migrants through systematic rights violations including of the *non-refoulement* principle (pushbacks) by Niger and the lack of human rights safeguards in the context of the Integrated Border Management (IBM)²³³ Project (financed by the EU Regional Trust Fund).

7.2.2. Causation

When outsourcing the management of refugees from countries suffering attacks by terrorist groups in the region (notably Nigeria, Mali, Burkina Faso) and those located on Libyan territory, the EU has developed a proactive policy to support Niger in migration and asylum governance. EU efforts have focused on building a national asylum system capable of containing refugees and strengthening border management²³⁴.

In the context of legal reforms aimed at strengthening security and border management in the region, the Nigerien government adopted Law 2015-36²³⁵ which criminalised irregular migration in accordance with Nigerien obligations stemming from the Palermo Protocol. It not only disturbed the effective possibility of internal movement in Niger for unregistered Nigeriens but also undermined freedom of movement of nationals from

²³³ On Frontex's future involvement see <https://www.statewatch.org/news/2022/march/frontex-to-boost-border-control-efforts-in-niger-algeria-and-libya/> ; <https://frontex.europa.eu/media-centre/news/news-release/frontex-signs-working-arrangement-with-eucap-sahel-niger-R8bj2Z> and https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/E-9-2023-000049_EN.html accessed 6 February 2023. On ICMPD role see <https://www.icmpd.org/our-work/projects/border-management-and-border-communities-in-the-sahel-region> and https://ec.europa.eu/trustfundforafrica/sites/default/files/summative_monitoring_report_eu_tf_north_of_africa_region_january_2017-march_2021_0.pdf accessed 6 February 2023.

²³⁴ https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eucap-sahel-niger/eucap-sahel-niger-field-missions-border-management_en accessed 6 February 2023.

²³⁵ NIGER Report; <https://migration-control.info/en/wiki/niger/> and <https://migrants-refugees.va/fr/blog/country-profile/niger/> accessed 6 February 2023.

ECOWAS countries. In addition, it has prevented refugees from fleeing conflicts and other types of violence in neighbouring countries such as Mali and Nigeria²³⁶.

Germany, France and Spain have been actively involved in security and border management in Niger. The GIZ project (ProGEM)²³⁷, the AFD project (AJUSEN)²³⁸ and the FIIAPP project²³⁹ aimed at creating a Joint Investigation Team (EJI) for the fight against irregular immigration, human trafficking and migrant smuggling. Considering that these are governmental agencies, it should be noted that their conduct could be attributable to the named states under Article 4 ARSIWA.

7.2.3. Responsibility attribution

Attribution of responsibility to Niger

Border surveillance as well as control of entry and residence in Niger rests with its executive organs, and thus the wrongful acts committed on its territory in the context of its close cooperation with the EU to manage refugee movements, are attributable to Niger under Article 4 ARSIWA. In particular, not having acted in conformity with its human rights obligations regarding the prohibition of *refoulement* and the right to leave as enshrined in the Refugee Convention, the ACHPR and the ICCPR, Niger is in breach of its international obligations under Articles 12 and 13 ARSIWA.

²³⁶ See the complaint filed in May 2022 against the State of Niger before the ECOWAS Court of Justice alleging systematic human rights violations in Niger stemming from the implementation of Law 36-2015. For further information see

- <https://sciabacaoruka.asgi.it/fr/conference-de-presse-niger-plainte-deposee-contre-la-loi-qui-criminalise-le-transit-des-migrants/>
- <https://www.ohchr.org/en/documents/country-reports/note-trimestrielle-publique-sur-les-tendances-de-la-situation-des-droits>

²³⁷ <https://www.giz.de/en/worldwide/315.html> accessed 6 February 2023.

²³⁸ <https://www.afd.fr/en/page-region-pays/niger> accessed 6 February 2023.

²³⁹ <https://www.border-security-report.com/the-spanish-national-police-and-the-fiiapp-combat-human-trafficking-in-nigeria-and-niger/> accessed 6 February 2023.

Attribution of conduct to the EU and to individual Member States for complicity

In light of earlier analysis, it is arguable that support in the context of its surveillance activities may amount to 'aid or assistance'. Surveillance activities through which the Nigerien authorities detect migrants moving to Niger can be considered as a 'significant contribution' to the commission of human rights violations by the Nigerien authorities. In addition, it could be argued that the requirement of the causal link between these acts of aid or assistance and internationally wrongful acts seems to be fulfilled. Arguably, a sufficient degree of causal relation exists between the aid in the form of surveillance support on the one hand, and the rejection at the border and pullback of migrants by Nigerien authorities on the other. To put it simply, it would not be possible for the Nigerien authorities to detect and locate migrants at the border without the surveillance support provided by the EU and individual Member States.

As regards the knowledge requirement, the situation at the borders is well-documented by various organisations, NGOs and other commentators. It could be argued that the EU is likely to know about the commission of the internationally wrongful acts against migrants in and out of Niger (knowledge of the possibility / risk of human rights violations and acceptance). Finally, the question of whether both the EU and Niger are bound by the same obligation can be answered in the affirmative, particularly in cases where the breached international obligations implicate the right to life, right to asylum, the prohibition of *refoulement*, and the prohibition of collective expulsions.

The above considered, aid or assistance to Niger in the form of border management may amount to the formal responsibility of the EU and of individual Member States by complicity under Articles 14 ARIO and 16 ARSIWA.

Attribution based on concerted action

As mentioned earlier, international responsibility for aid and assistance under ARSIWA rests on similar premises with shared responsibility for concerted action under GPSRIL. Responsibility arises as long as the international person involved in concerted action has knowledge of the circumstances of the internationally wrongful act, the conduct contributes to the indivisible injury of another person, and the act would be internationally wrongful if committed by the international person taking part in the concerted action. In the case of aid and assistance under ARSIWA, the international legal responsibility has a derivative nature, and therefore the primary responsibility rests with Niger, whereas secondary responsibility lies with the EU and with individual EU Member States based on their supporting role to the extent that their financing and active involvement in border management have contributed to human rights violations on the ground. In terms of the opposability requirement, Principle 7 GPSRIL is relevant. Violations of relevant provisions under the Refugee Convention, the ICCPR, and the ECHR may constitute the basis for the internationally wrongful acts in question.

7.3. CASE 3: Systemic responsibility with respect to the containment of refugee movements in Niger

7.3.1. Wrongful act

The wrongful acts identified in this case of systemic responsibility allocation consist of violation of the right to leave, the right to seek asylum and *non-refoulement*.

7.3.2. Causation

As noted earlier, European pressures have led the Nigerien authorities to tighten the conditions of entry and stay for migrants (e.g. restrictions in the transportation of migrants by private companies; intensifying border controls and introducing internal checkpoints; increased use of detention), meaning to prevent migrants from travelling northwards. EU–Niger negotiations resulted in several measures introduced in the Nigerien system (such as the IBM system of border control, imposition of documentation requirements, identification of asylum-seeking persons, reception of refugees).

These negotiations have been criticised as furthering EU interests in stopping onward migration from West Africa as a whole. Measures, such as border control and concentration of evacuees in Niger have been seen as an attempt to turn the country into a buffer zone for migration towards Europe. In particular, political involvement of the EU in migration governance in Niger and the region more broadly has led to the disruption of an existing regulated system of mobility, i.e. ECOWAS²⁴⁰ by another system of ambiguous character, resulting in internal instability and structural inequality.

In particular, flagrant violations of human rights have been reported, e.g. at the borders with Libya and Algeria as well as violation of freedom of movement as enshrined, among others, in the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights and ECOWAS Protocol on the Free Movement of Persons²⁴¹. These instruments contain obligations for actors bound by them, or may reflect obligations in general international law.

²⁴⁰ The Heads of State and Government of fifteen West African Countries established the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) when they signed the ECOWAS Treaty on the 28 May 1975 in Lagos, Nigeria. With new developments and mandates for the Community a revised treaty was signed in Cotonou, Benin Republic in July, 1993. The member states are Benin, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Côte d'Ivoire, The Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Sénégal and Togo. Also, Mauritania signed a new associate-membership agreement in August 2017. The aim of the Community is to promote cooperation and integration, leading to the establishment of an economic union in West Africa; a borderless region where the population has access to its abundant resources and is able to exploit them through the creation of opportunities under a sustainable environment. For details see <https://ecowas.int/about-ecowas/> accessed 6 February 2023.

²⁴¹ 1979 Protocol A/P.1/5/79 relating to Free Movement of Persons, Residence and Establishment.

7.3.3. Responsibility attribution

Attribution under ILC rules

As much as the financial instruments were meant to help Niger cope with the humanitarian crisis in its territory, they have essentially ensured that refugees and asylum seekers are contained there, alleviating pressures for EU countries at the EU's external borders. In that sense, financial responsibility of the EU for financing border management in Niger may be possible. However, the EU's role in EU–Niger cooperation has remained at the level of financial support and no direct involvement of the EU or its partners in alleged human rights violations can be established. Thus, it is rather hard for the requirements for formal responsibility attribution to be fulfilled primarily due to evidentiary problems.

Attribution based on concerted action

Systemic responsibility attributable to the EU because of its broader political involvement of the EU in migration governance in Niger and ECOWAS is broadly possible here. In particular, systemic responsibility captures the containment / deterrence perspective, emphasised in the NIG Report. As noted by Tinni, Hamadou, and Spijkerboer, the European containment strategy in this case has a twofold face: while its aim is to strengthen Niger's capacity to host refugees and asylum seekers, and provide a path to resettlement, asylum seekers, who have not been recognised as refugees and thus have not been resettled, and who have been living in limbo in Niger for years, are transported from Libya to Niger. If we add to the equation that some of these asylum seekers have been transported to Libya as part of the EUTF-funded 'pullbacks', the question is whether this chain of activities – made possible by the EU – is contrary to the prohibition of *refoulement* and collective expulsion (see e.g. ECHR's *Hirsi Jamaa v Italy* judgment)²⁴².

EU leverage in this context stems from the dependence of less affluent countries on development aid that has become the main channel of funding migration control via the EUTF. West African countries face the challenge of adhering to the EU's migration control agenda, while at the same time ensuring free movement in ECOWAS and implementing their obligations of *non-refoulement*.

In light of the above, the ETM can be seen as a mechanism promoting the controlled mobility of refugees to resettlement countries, but also as a mechanism promoting containment (pullback to Libya, evacuation, resettlement at the discretion of European countries). The same applies for the establishment of an asylum procedure in Agadez. The possibility to receive asylum in Niger – even if resettlement is not applicable – is a positive development for the mobility of refugees, especially considering the torture-like situation in Libya they were faced with. However, the fact that these people are transferred from Libya, Sudan, and Chad to Niger and that some of them will not be able to move further, turns the city into 'a waiting space', exacerbating precarity. In this sense, the case is similar to Türkiye and Tunisia, in that the EU has shaped Nigerien migration policy in the direction of controlling the movement of refugees, essentially depriving them from deciding

²⁴² NIGER Report.

themselves their migration journey with no guarantee that protection through resettlement would be secured.

In light of the above, a systemic approach to responsibility attribution focuses on the wider involvement of the EU and its Member States in migration governance in Niger. Similar to Türkiye, Tunisia, and Serbia, the EU has shaped Nigerien migration policy in the direction of preventing refugees from entering the EU and its Member States spontaneously through the sub-Saharan Africa route (deterrence), of keeping rejected refugees there (containment), and of allowing for contained mobility to resettlement countries. This has resulted in systematic migrant rights violations, as emphasised above²⁴³. Arguably, this form of hypercomplex concerted action has been chosen by the EU and its Member States with (direct) intent to evade attribution under ILC rules.

7.4. CASE 4: Systemic responsibility with respect to coproduction of refugee movements originating from Libya

7.4.1. Wrongful act

The wrongful acts identified in this case of systemic responsibility attribution consist of human rights violations as a result of deficiencies in protection, reception, and border management systems in Niger.

7.4.2. Causation

The first Libyan Civil War that led to the toppling of Muammar Gaddafi's regime was largely the result of support provided by the international coalition (to which NATO contributed most resources) to the different military forces of the National Transition Council that opposed Gaddafi. The two opposing parties benefit from official and unofficial diplomatic support of foreign powers. The European countries officially stand by the UN Security Council, who established an embargo with the 1970/2011 Resolution, 'in order to prevent the direct or indirect supply, selling or transfer' of weapons,

²⁴³ The European Ombudsman has acknowledged the possible human rights impact of EUTF projects noting that the usage of surveillance technologies by the partner countries may go beyond the purposes foreseen under the EUTF project, which may entail a 'risk for human rights of individuals in these countries, as well as for the ability of the EU to fulfil or realise its human rights obligations', European Ombudsman, Decision on how the European Commission assessed the human rights impact before providing support to African countries to develop surveillance capabilities (case 1904/2021/MHZ) p. 5, available at <https://www.ombudsman.europa.eu/en/decision/en/163491>. The Ombudsman found it 'regrettable that the EUTFA projects in question were not subject to a clear human rights impact assessment' by the Commission. See pages 6-7. On the human rights consequences of omitting impact assessment contrary to the principles of loyal and sincere cooperation and the principle of good administration, see also Sergio Carrera, Juan Santos Vara and Tineke Strik, 'The external dimensions of EU migration and asylum policies in times of crisis' in *Constitutionalising the External Dimensions of EU Migration Policies in Times of Crisis L equality, Rule of Law and Fundamental Rights Reconsidered* (Edwar Elgar Publishing 2019).

ammunition, and similar materials, and had called for political negotiations in 2015²⁴⁴. Nevertheless, this has been seen as a fake neutrality, which in fact leaves space for European states' divided interests on the matter to be pursued²⁴⁵.

7.4.3. Responsibility attribution

Attribution of responsibility to EU Member States

The above considered, a systemic approach to responsibility attribution would focus on the wider context preceding the EU-Nigerien government cooperation for the purposes of establishing the ETM. An argument can be made that EU Member States have triggered refugee movements from Libya, through their involvement in the Libyan war, be it funding NATO operations, or supporting relevant UN action. As identified above, the source of responsibility for the EU and NATO-participating EU Member States, is their contribution to coproduction of refugee movements originating from Libya through their political and military involvement in the Libyan war guided by their colonial and postcolonial connections with the region.

²⁴⁴ Resolution 1970 (2011) / adopted by the Security Council at its 6491st meeting, on 26 February 2011, S/RES/1970 (2011).

²⁴⁵ Florian Laur, Translated by Giulia Querini 'The EU and the Libyan Conundrum', 20 May 2020 at <https://www.taurillon.org/the-eu-and-the-libyan-conundrum?lang=fr> accessed 6 February 2023.

8. Conclusions

The effectiveness of the UN Global Compact on Refugees (GCR) depends on increased cooperation among various parties for the protection of refugees. One interest the EU pursues through its collaboration with third states such as Türkiye, Tunisia, Serbia and Niger, and with international organisations such as the UNHCR and IOM, is that of collectivised migration control. However, such collaboration may result in *excessive complexity*, making it difficult to discern the extent of each party's involvement and to attribute responsibility for wrongful acts. Where collaboration rests on *informal* arrangements, attributing responsibility becomes more challenging. Reduced accountability may be one of the reasons for engaging in such conduct.

However, debates and developments in the law of international responsibility have begun to address the problem of potential responsibility evasion through collective conduct. Apart from the ILC articles, international lawyers can today base their arguments on the codification effort of the GPSRIL, or on the analyses of single international law writers who seek to address the problem of responsibility loss by emphasising the collective, or systemic, aspects of responsibility attribution. When the EU works through third parties, these progressive developments in international law augment the risk of being met with arguments that place a share of responsibility at its door. It is these risks that the present report seeks to identify.

In the preceding pages, we have outlined the debatable aspect of responsibility attribution under international law for violations of individual rights in the context of migratory movements and migration control. We applied an approach drawing on international law at large, and its second-order norms on responsibility in particular, rather than on one that takes human rights law and institutions, or refugee law and its institutional superstructure as a point of departure. This choice has led us to consider attribution rather than jurisdiction. Why should we resort to the level of international law today?

At that level, the continuing heritage of European colonial history in the formulation of international legal norms was and continues to be debated. TWAIL researchers have articulated positions from the vantage point of the Global South. Claims for reparations for colonial injustices now command much more attention than a decade ago. Taking their cue from the question of climate justice, calls for 'migration justice' have been articulated in ways that reach beyond the limited domains of human rights and refugee law. Even in mainstream debates, there is a growing emphasis that 'bilateralist' accounts of international law no longer do justice to the multilateral practice of international law, and perhaps never did. In summary, these debates revolve around the shirking of responsibility: historical, legal, or both. Choosing an international law approach for this report strengthened the connections between individual rights violations in the migratory context, in particular where they occur with a degree of systematicity, and these wider debates about responsibility evasion. These connections are important, because they shape the political landscape in which North-South relations in migration play out, and where the EU may experience blowback against unsustainable models of cooperation.

In our country-specific analysis of attribution arguments, we always found attribution to the territorial state arguable under Article 4 ARSIWA. While this is a trivial result, we found it relevant to underscore the risks borne by territorial states in the implementation of migrant control measures

We have studied possible attribution arguments in the context of substandard protection and reception of migrants, including refugees, for cases related to all four countries. We found support for attribution arguments in various provisions of ARSIWA and ARIO for situations in Türkiye, Tunisia and Niger. While ILC articles did not provide a sufficient basis for attribution arguments in Serbia, such arguments could be based on Principle 7 GPSRIL.

Containment of refugee movements in cases related to all four countries was another unit of analysis. Attribution proved arguable under ILC articles in the case of Türkiye and Tunisia. For Niger, Principle 7 GPSRIL offered a pathway towards attribution in parallel to an attribution argument based on a systemic approach. In the case of Serbia, the sole avenue for an attribution argument was based on the systemic approach. Neither ILC articles nor the GPSRIL offered stepping stones for attribution in that category of cases.

For Serbia and Niger respectively, we looked into attribution arguments for human rights violations in the course of border management. In the case of Serbia, we found that conduct for which the EU is the principal actor was not attributable under ILC articles. If the EU is regarded as a complicit actor, attribution under Article 14 ARIO is arguable.

For the cases of coproduction of refugee movements from Syria (related to our analysis of Türkiye) and from Libya (related to our analysis of Tunisia and Niger respectively), we found that arguments based on a systemic approach to attribution could plausibly be articulated, but that neither ILC articles nor the GPSRIL offered a base for tenable arguments.

A comprehensive conclusion drawn from the analysis of all country cases and categories is that the EU and its Member States are at a considerable risk of encountering arguments regarding the attribution of responsibility for violations of individual rights in the context of migration control. These arguments are based on attribution norms as outlined in the ILC articles or in the GPSRIL. Such arguments are likely to emerge in the diplomatic interplay between South and North, as well as in public critiques of EU policies, in particular in the Global South. It is beyond our mandate to specify institutional pathways for potential claims resting on such arguments, but it should not be ruled out that these are identified and used, for example in strategic litigation. Moreover, it is important to consider that new arguments on responsibility attribution, based on a systemic approach, may be developed. These arguments could potentially affect the development of the law of international responsibility possibly reducing its historical bias in favour of Northern states.

Over time, the law will catch up with those seeking to evade it. In its future third party collaborations on migration control and containment within or beyond the UN GCR framework, the EU and its Member States should be mindful that the law of international responsibility has developed in ways that obliterate lacunae in attribution and continues to do so.

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